

Borders Shaping
Perceptions of European Societies

Deliverable Report

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Executive Summary

The aim of this report is to discuss the state of the art on how borders shape borderlanders' perceptions of Europe and the European project. It outlines the main theoretical approaches and research findings to identify gaps and provide a solid basis for the empirical analysis of the B-SHAPES project. It is argued that living in borderlands and being exposed to 'others' shapes the way residents imagine and internalise Europe. However, following the constructivist conceptualisation of borders, which are not only located at territorial edges but are also created in discourses, narratives, and practices, we argue that borderlanders' perceptions of Europe are influenced not only by everyday life in border regions, but also by macro-narratives of polycrisis and the ways in which people on the move, securitisation policies and (in)securities are categorised and framed. Thus, the report focuses on three crucial events that may influence public perceptions and the European imaginary: the 'migration crisis', re-bordering trends related to the Covid-19 pandemic, and the European elections. Accordingly, the first three sections summarise the literature on border perceptions in the context of these upheavals. However, it is clear from the literature review that borderlanders' perceptions of Europe have been little explored by scholars. This is where B-SHAPES comes in, addressing the question of how Europe is framed and narratively constructed from below. Subsequently, sections 4-6 provide an overview of publications on Eurosceptics, minorities, and natural and cultural landscapes from the perspective of borderlands studies, to anchor our empirical investigation in existing research and to go beyond the state of the art. It is worth noting that we consider 'borderlanders' not only as people living in border regions, but also as rhetorical figures created in public discourses. Nevertheless, the report acknowledges that borderlanders' narratives and perceptions of Europe should be considered as dynamic processes that are subject to constant change. Therefore, B-SHAPES will capture borderlanders' attitudes towards Europe at a particular moment in time, shaped by current events and discourses.

1. Introduction

B-SHAPES applies the concept of perception as a powerful dimension of the social construction of reality (Friedman, 2011), defined as perspectives (Shibutani, 1955), frames (Goffman, 1974), or habitus (Bourdieu, 1996; Bourdieu and Thompson, 1991). It emphasises that perceptions are created in the socialisation process through both group membership and individual experience. Thus, perceptions are influenced by national education systems, cultural policies, public discourse, and collective memory. By evaluating the literature on citizens' attitudes towards Europe, Gaxie (2013) identifies three approaches. The first is the utilitarian approach, which assumes that the more individuals benefit from European construction, the more positive they will be towards the European integration process. In this respect, education, professional skills, and income could have an impact on European attachment. The second perspective - the value-based explanations - emphasises that support for Europe increases when there is a sense of belonging to Europe. In contrast, citizens with an exclusive national identity often have negative attitudes towards European integration. Finally, the third explanation is based on the national context. It argues that national differences in support for European integration are more significant than individual or ideological differences. National

visions of Europe are based on national political culture, which is created by politicians and journalists and represented in macro-narratives.

Against this background, the study of perceptions allows us to gain knowledge about people's norms, feelings of belonging, their values and national collective perceptions of the European project, which determine citizens' attitudes and practices. In this respect, residents of border regions may differ from citizens of core regions, as geography still matters (Nasr and Rieger, 2023). According to the European Committee of the Regions, about 150 million people (about a third of the population of the European Union) live in European border regions (EC, 2021). European border regions have become centres of cross-border cooperation, of free movement and of transnational exchange. Thus, border residents are exposed to the "other/neighbours" and cultural transfer on a daily base. However, as Nasr and Rieger (2023, 2) argue, "interaction with strangers can contribute to the emergence of multilayered identities, but it can also reinforce cultural differences and disparities". Thus, the borderland effect is ambivalent in nature - borderland residents may be more open and tolerant of 'others' or more closed and xenophobic.

When analysing public perception of borders, it can be argued that this is usually studied through surveys conducted at the national or European level (e.g. Eurostat, European Social Survey, Eurobarometer). In this respect, an interesting insight is provided by Nasr and Rieger (2023). By matching data from the European NUTS-level Election Database and Eurobarometer and comparing border regions with core regions, they argue that Eurosceptic parties perform better in border constituencies and that border residents have more negative attitudes towards the EU (see more in chapter 4). However, this quantitative approach must rely on consistent measures of Euroscepticism such as vote share of Eurosceptic parties or responses to standardised survey questionnaires. Such an approach is useful for comparative analysis but necessarily misses many nuances. In contrast, B-SHAPES uses qualitative methods to explore how residents of border regions perceive the European project and Europe as a socio-cultural entity.

It is worth noting that in recent decades, discussions on the condition of Europe have been embedded in the framework of crisis or even polycrisis (Lawrance, Janzwood, Homer-Dixon, 2022). Since the beginning of the 21st century, multidimensional and interdependent crises with different characteristics have become widespread in European public debate - be it the financial/monetary crisis in the Eurozone, the security crisis, the ecological/climate crisis, the welfare state crisis, the crisis of liberal democracy, the Covid-19 pandemic crisis, the crisis of European integration, or the crisis of the idea of Europe as such. Among these many crises, the migration crisis, refugee crisis, humanitarian crisis, or border crisis have been used in the debate as close or even synonymous terms, even if their specific meaning is far from identical. The first general feature of the discourse on the proliferation of never-ending crises is their normalisation. While the term 'crisis' suggests sudden, exceptional, anomalous, temporary, and surprising situations to be overcome in the future, the current framing of social reality sees crisis as an ordinary, normalised, permanent, and everyday condition (Walby, 2015). If crisis has become the normalised state of exception, what is normalcy? How do we imagine a state of non-crisis? For the European borderlands, we can ask: how would they function in a non-crisis reality? The adoption of the crisis framework almost automatically invokes the

image of a good but lost normalcy that can (and should) be reclaimed. The causes of the crisis should be tamed, removed, and resolved. Regardless of whether the supposed entity in crisis is a European border or borderland, the crisis narrative leads to anti-crisis solutionism.

The aim of this report is to provide an overview of the most important studies on the perceptions of borderland inhabitants to identify research gaps and to lay the foundation for our own empirical research. The report is structured as follows: The first section examines the scholarship on perceptions of border(s) and Europe embedded in the debate on the ‘migration crisis’. It demonstrates the persistent ambivalence of the border function as fence and bridge, and summarises the scholarship on de-territorialised, transgressed borders and amorphous borderlands. It also reflects on borderwork, border culture, and border activism as significant concepts for understanding the everyday lives of borderlanders. With the consequences of the Covid-19 pandemic-related re-bordering policies in mind, the second section reviews and summarises scholarly work on borderland responses, crisis management, and performative actions against border restrictions. Applying the resilience approach, some studies suggest that the crisis could also act as a catalyst for strengthening cross-border cooperation and European identification, which is highlighted in section 2.3. Section 3 is devoted to the question of how political groups in the European Parliament and political parties in EU countries frame and envisage borders. It is argued that borders are mostly seen as security lines and Europe as a ‘gated community’. After reviewing the literature on the three crucial factors shaping European perceptions, the next three sections focus on presenting the state of the art for the B-SHAPES case studies. Section 4 discusses Euroscepticism from a borderlands’ studies perspective. In addition, Section 5 outlines how scholarship explores European perceptions of minorities. Finally, section 6 highlights how scholars are dealing with borderlands as cultural and natural heritage. The report ends with some conclusions that recapitulate the main findings of the overall literature review and indicate research gaps that B-SHAPES aims to fill.

2. Re-bordering in the context of the migration crisis shaping Borderlanders’ perceptions of Europe

The ‘migration crisis’ became one of the dominant discursive frames through which the European borderlands were seen by others and regarded themselves. Before we examine how the recent literature from the realm of border studies, migration studies, or European studies view the borderlands through the lenses of the ‘migration crisis’ after 2015, we would like to start with a few general remarks on this particular discourse.

Firstly, as outlined above, the adoption and then normalisation of crisis framing marginalises and erases the alternative discourses and – in effect – alternative actions and policies. The researchers of the discourse of the European ‘migration crisis’ analysed how it was produced and when, how it was internalised as an almost natural condition, and then how it made competing stories unthinkable. Jørgensen (2022, 23-42) offered a general chronology of discursive construction of the ‘migration crisis’. The author points out that in the beginning of events which soon were to be labelled as a ‘migration crisis’, the EU institutions preferred to speak of the ‘crisis of solidarity’ or the adaptation of the Schengen system to new circumstances. Then the crisis logic came to the forefront and launched the discursive

reframing which ultimately resulted in the securitisation and militarisation of the European borderlands. If the story of a 'crisis of solidarity' was part of the call to offer more solidarity, and the discussion of weaknesses of the Schengen system suggested that Europe is responsible for the disarray, injustice and suffering on its borders, then the subsequent crisis narratives shifted the focus from the 'crisis of Europe' to 'the crisis in Europe', this time provoked by external threats which had to be tamed. The frame of the 'refugee crisis' shifted the terms of debate from solidarity to that of protection of deserving subjects ('the real refugees'). Then, discourse about a 'humanitarian crisis' further reinforced the apolitical and paternalistic approach and legitimised the practice of dividing the deserving subjects from the undeserving ones (e.g. refugees from 'economic migrants'). Instead of universal protection, the exclusivist and selective differentiation of people on the move provoked even more risky and desperate tactics to get to Europe, and this reinforced the scale of the 'humanitarian crisis'. The more people remained outside the exclusionary policies, the more they were vulnerable to dangerous border crossings, violence from smugglers and security guards, or the hardships of choosing new routes to Europe. In effect, more securitised and militarised solutions were adopted – with the declared aim of 'saving life'.

According to Jørgensen's study (Jørgensen, 2022, 23-42), the humanitarian approach added new layers to the 'migration crisis' narrative. Now migration or mobility as such were seen as the basis of the crisis, bringing chaos, unpredictability, and insecurity. In order to effectively deal with the 'migration crisis', Europe was called upon to strengthen and redesign its borders. The language of 'border tensions', 'borders under pressure', 'siege at Europe's gates', or 'leaky borders' supplemented the 'migration crisis' with the story of the 'border crisis'. If new borders were in crisis, then this discourse legitimised their fencing, externalising to neighbouring countries, securitising with new surveillance technologies, and strengthening with new archipelagos of containment. The securitisation of borders brought anxieties over the 'Schengen crisis' - re-borderings not only outside the EU, but also internally, through the reappearance of border controls and new technologies of controlling the movement of people and brought into doubt the possibility of sustaining the freedom of flows. The last act of this domino effect of crisis-driven discourses was the perception that maybe the re-borderings are the manifestations of the EU's crisis or the crisis of the idea of Europe as such (Jørgensen, 2022). The self-perpetuating policies of securitisation of borders which were projected to save Europe may be challenging for its future.

Secondly, the framing of the 'migration crisis', which resulted in a border crisis and then in borders' securitisation, had serious consequences for the European borderlands. Stępa (2022) demonstrated how the 'migration crisis' as policy framing led to a policing approach focused on providing remedial actions. The paradigm of systemic risk management of borders and migration, together with the policies of exceptionalist security – such as fencing, introducing states of exceptions, or employing push-backs of migrants – supplemented the humanitarian approach. The security of migrants and borders was used to legitimise solutionism of this kind. The new role of the EU's borderlands was to play a crucial role in reframing the migrants as the objects of risk. Through hotspots, detention centres, and other re-borderings the borderlands were on the forefront of the securitised approach.

Thirdly, and finally, it is the shifting role of the European borderland during this period, and how this manifests itself in the perception of its inhabitants, that we intend to grasp in our project. However, one final observation is of vital importance here: the securitisation of European borderlands, under the pressure of the 'migration crisis' narratives, changed their

meaning and geography. While in our research we bring into focus selected borderlands, understood as lying at the junction of the national territories, the contemporary literature on the European borderlands never ceases to underline that the narrative of the ‘migration crisis’ and its policies, reorganised the understanding of borderlands and borderlanders.

The overall result of the crisis approach was the transformation of the European space into one big hot spot, or an amorphous borderland. Although the rationale of securitisation was to protect the territory and the people from chaos outside, Europe had to externalise its borderlands beyond the realm of its territory, and to construct new spaces of bordering internally in order to control the criminalised and illegalised unauthorised movement. As a result, the bordering of the people and the ‘others’ increasingly happens not only at the borders in the sense of the lines at the end of territory (or in the borderlands). Hot spots – the sites of identification and differentiation of people on the move – overlap with the European space, and the limits of this space are far from clear and established: “the hotspot nomenclature hints at modes of governmental intervention that are predicated on the discursive register of the crisis and contribute to reshaping the very image of what a border is—shifting from a linear conceptualisation of the border as a national frontier toward a mobile and punctual constellation of critical border zones. From this perspective, the European space can be remapped according to the fabrication of such border sites of crisis, which eventually appear as ‘trouble spots’ due to the recalcitrant presence of migrants and consequently are securitised into ‘hotspots’ through the implementation of detention infrastructures and identification procedures” (De Genova, Garelli, Tazzioli 2018, 255).

Accordingly, the scholars of the European borderlands speak of geographies which must be mapped anew, beyond supposedly ocular and deceptive appearances. Lagios, Lekka, and Panoutsopoulos (2018, 47) argue that the influential metaphor of the ‘fortress Europe’ is less accurate today than ‘gated community Europe’ because the main rationale of the EU’s border regime is not to stop the people on the move in its borderlands (even if these are currently re-walled), but it is rather devoted to hierarchising, differentiating, and regulating the subject in the social body. Instead of having clear borderlands, located on the edges of territory where bordering procedures are fulfilled (as in the figure of the fortress), contemporary Europe becomes its own borderland which – through the constant diffusion of borders – filters who is included and who is excluded, or – even more accurately – who is included as included, who is included as excluded (marginalised), and who is deemed as surplus.

We follow the conclusions worked out in *BordEUR* project’s report on *New European Borderlands*. The authors argue that ‘bordering and fortification were the EU’s and member states’ primary policy responses to mass migration (both internal and external) and led to three ways in which new border(land)s were created: the reemergence of physical borders within the Union (most notably the reintroduction of borders within the Schengen zone); the creation of ‘New Borderlands’ through externalisation; and the redrawing of borders through Brexit’ (BordEUR, 2022: 10). The researchers claim that the construction of new EU borderlands challenged two grand narratives which the EU maintained about itself: (1) the progressive narrative on the expanding integration in the face of crises; (2) the normative soft power of the EU over its neighbours. The ‘migrant crisis’ discourse and policies challenged both narratives: instead of transcending borders through integration and soft power, it resulted in their proliferation and strengthening: “We understand borders both in the physical sense, but also in their soft sense, i.e., as symbolic boundaries about the limits of political communities—be it

on the state or European level—that are used to naturalise hard borders. We equally highlight how, due to the EU’s peculiarities, bordering does not exclusively take place at state borders, but also in new locales: airports, travel agencies, the internet, and of course, in third countries” (BordEUr, 2022, 10).

The vacillation of borders provokes the oxymoronic condition in which the border shifts from the edge of the political to its centre, and it becomes – as a site of both exclusion and inclusion, division and unification – the laboratory of new forms of social life (Trimikliniotis, 2022, 182). *The Atlas of Migration in Europe*, published by Migreurop (2019), provides a detailed cartography of the new European borderland and the social practices it provokes. This cartography is composed of sites as diverse as spaces of confinements, slums, jungles, camps, hospitable towns, rebel cities, humanitarian corridors, return houses, squats, networks of volunteer associations. This new mapping of borderlands has important consequences for the identification of the figure of the borderlander. If borderlands are de-territorialised, externalised, internalised, offshored, digitalised etc., then who inhabits them? While this overview of the contemporary literature includes also the research conducted in borderlands in their traditional meaning as territorial spaces, it expands the scope to take into account the actors who deal with the new de-territorialised borderlands: e.g. Africans who experience the externalisation of EU’s borderlands to their countries, people on the move and activists who gained insights into the practical workings of the EU’s border regimes, authors of textual, visual and digital narratives of transgressing the EU’s borders, participants in political mobilisations for debordering and re-borderings, or local stakeholders who see their borderlands as sites of a possible Europeanisation of solidarity, hospitality or identity. The borderlander will be understood in this section in a wide way: as a subject who is produced, moved, displaced, expelled, included, controlled, or driven to action by bordering.

2.1. Discussions around migration crisis from the perspective of borderlanders

Borderlands are sites of everyday processes of bordering de- and re-bordering – constantly oscillating between the role of being a bridge and a barrier. In the context of the ‘migration crisis’ which results in rapid and sometimes unexpected re/deborderings, these bridges and barriers are opened and closed, lifted and lowered, abolished and built, restored and transgressed, surveyed and freed, etc. Boesen (2017, 2-3), in her introduction to the study of social life in the European borderlands, argues that one-sided stories of the gradual disappearance of borders or the persistence of stable divisions turned out not to be true. Opening the borders in Europe did not lead to their abolition but was supplemented by novel forms of borderings. While proximity towards the Other is the peculiar feature of the borderland, and its effects may be the development of inclusive border culture or more universalist border identity – also the European one – this scenario is far from guaranteed. Contrary to Euroenthusiastic hopes, cross-border relations and everyday life in Europe did not lead to erasure of borders, and it created opportunities for both integration and tensions.

One of the most pronounced and recent phenomena which flourished in the context of ‘migration crisis’ framing, is the rise of cross-border national populism. Mazzoleni (2023) used the case study of Swiss national populism to examine the strategies of construction of borders

in the populist discourses on the nation/the people. Populist discourses are organised around dividing the people from the internal and external others, such as detached cosmopolitan elites, supranational bodies and corporations, or foreign populations. Boundaries are the symbolic devices which are used to construct the people and their outside. In the case of literal border/lands, they often became sites of populist mobilisation – while located at the margins of the nation state, they may be utilised as endangered heartlands which have to be protected. Borders play three main roles in populist strategies. Firstly, borders are issues to which populists refer directly (as in the case of stopping immigration), or indirectly (e.g. in the discussions on international treaties). Secondly, borders are narratives and symbolic constructions utilised in the identitarian construction of ‘Us’ and ‘Them’: those who do not value or defend ‘ours’ borders may be depicted as ‘Them’. Thirdly, borders may be territorial spaces for populist mobilisations, e.g. protest against immigration, or manifestations of national identity. The ‘migration crisis’ is regarded by national populists as an opportunity to refer to all three meanings of borders in order to construct their vision of the people. Similar observations are offered in the case of Hungarian populism by Sata (2020) who argues that it adopts the frames which radically divide the people from the elite and from strangers. The core element of the framing is ‘often a romantic myth of a homogeneous nation. Other traditional themes and frames associated with populist discourse are the reference to crisis, breakdown or threat; an appeal to the people; its anti-establishment, anti-elite character; and the bad manners that have entered public talk’ (Sata, 2020, 55). The discourse on the European ‘migration crisis’, shared also by the mainstream parties, makes the populist framings easier and more convincing to the public.

But borders could be used as a resource also for non-populist/anti-populist purposes. The research team led by Müller (2023) examined how local authorities in the borderlands take advantage of the opportunities for cross-border cooperation. Their study, conducted in two Euroregions in the Polish-German-Czech and the Czech-German-Austrian borderlands, was focused on how the local mayors conceive borders in their policies: as bridges or obstacles. The authors differentiated between passive and active borders. The former played a role in the construction of a closed and ‘sacred’ identity, based on negative relations with the neighbours, polarity of us/them, stereotyping, and understanding of politics in terms of rivalry. The latter, on the contrary, contributed to the development of a diverse identity, inclusive of the Other, and resulted in cross-border cooperation. Thus, active borders are regarded as the vehicles of Europeanisation because they permit recognising differences and constructing unity at the same time.

The need to supersede the securitised framing of border politics is recognised not only in internal borderlands of the EU. In the Euromed survey (Gabrielli, Aragal, 2016) 5,900 experts from the countries belonging to the Union for the Mediterranean were asked to share their perception of the migrant and refugee situation in the Mediterranean. During the 2015-2016 period the region became the most important borderland acting as a stage for the ‘migration crisis’. Curiously, their opinion was clearly marked by the sense of structural reasons lying at the root of migration. Not migration as such, but the deeper processes such as the war in Syria, destabilisation of Libya, the lack of perspectives for African people, or the migration and refugee policy in the EU, were identified as issues to be addressed. These findings show that – at least in the early phase of the what-was-to-become ‘migration crisis’ - the experts had the framings which potentially paved the way for a different approach from the securitisation of

borders. Another interesting finding was that the reasons behind migration were seen differently depending on the location of the respondents: those who lived close to the Eastern migration route to the EU expected that military conflicts would be the most important factor, and the inhabitants of the Western route were of the opinion that socio-economic conditions would contribute the most. In the conclusion of the report, its authors pointed out the need to drop the securitisation paradigm and to recognise migration as a structural feature of the Mediterranean. More possibilities of legal migration and more solutions based on rights for migrants, were seen as the basis for rebuilding the European borderlands beyond the 'migration crisis' framing.

The research led by Vaughan-Williams (2023) examines how such framing was adopted by the European public and legitimised the securitisation of borders. The project, based on qualitative research, including 24 focus groups with 179 EU citizens between 2016 and 2017 across 11 cities and 5 countries, offers a study of bottom-up vernacular perceptions of the European 'migration crisis'. The majority of the researched subjects adhere to the view that their ontological security is endangered, and borders play crucial role in rebuilding it. The citizens' perception of the 'migration crisis' transforms the whole of Europe into a borderland in which borders are under pressure and the lack of security is felt. At the same time, the rising securitisation of borders does not result in the level of security it promised. On the contrary, more securitisation increases the sense of danger, and it produces the migrant figures of strangeness and anxiety such as the terrorist, the sexual molester, the animalised subject. In the concluding remarks, the author argues that the de-securitisation of otherness is needed to get out of the vicious circle of border (in)securitisation which transforms Europe into a borderland.

We should supplement the depiction of the European 'migrant crisis' with the voices of those who faced the rise of the new European borderland: people on the move. In *Reclaiming Migration* Squire, Squire, Perkowski, Stevens, and Vaughan-Williams (2021) managed to conduct 257 interviews with the people who had made – or who had contemplated making – the dangerous journey across the Mediterranean Sea by boat. The authors understand their project as a counter-archive based on in-depth qualitative research across multiple sites during 2015 and 2016'. This counter-archive offers a competitive story about the 'migrant crisis'. Expectations of Europe collided here with reality as it was experienced by people on the move. Securitised migrants stressed three main tendencies in their journeys through the new European borderland: (1) securitisation made the migration even more risky and precarious; (2) humanitarianism reduces migrants to victims who need help, and mutes their voices and agency; (3) the securitisation which migrants faced was seen by them not as a sudden rupture (a crisis), but as a continuation of the colonial legacy of Europe. In sum, the 'migrant crisis' changed their perception of Europe: "While positive narratives exist, most of the people we spoke with were highly critical of what they perceived as the EU's failure to live up to its proclaimed values and principles." (Squire, Perkowski, Stevens and Vaughan-Williams 2021, 156).

The perception of the new EU's borderlands by borderlanders is now possible not only from the perspective of migrants but also from those who dwell in borderlands externalised by the EU to their countries of origin. This is the case of mobile borders which appear in the social life of non-mobile inhabitants. The concept of 'EurAfrican borders', coined by Gaibazzi, Bellagamba, and Dünwald (2017), refers to this phenomenon of "how much of Europe's

southern border is already in Africa. (...) The border has appeared in a multitude of places, forms and uniforms, in bilateral agreements and NGO programmes, in consulates and migrant camps, in joint police operations and activist campaigns” (Gaibazzi, Bellagamba and Dünnwald 2017, 4). While the export of EU’s borders has the aim to maintain and strengthen the divide between the EU and non-EU, they external proliferation results in blurring and hybridisation of clear boundaries. In the words of the authors: “especially for African borderlands scholars, ‘border zone’ can mean anything from bounded spaces such as fenced enclaves and consulates to unbounded ones like deserts and seas” (2017, 15). They argue that external frontiers of Europe create zones of contact, often unpredictable ones, with the African population, and in this way, they bring also possibilities of everyday de-borderings. What is more, the European externalisation of borders to African states is not one-sided. In order to fight against migrants who were ‘illegalised’ by the EU, it has to develop restrictive measures inside its territory. In effect, the EurAfrican borderland blurs itself not only in the sea, desert, or external controls but also in the geographical heart of Europe.

One of the most telling sites of EurAfrican borderings are the places in which the ‘migrant crisis’ left over the most suffering. In the account of Horsti (2023) the island of Lampedusa became the symbol of disastrous consequences of the ‘migrant crisis’. Being one site among many that were heavily affected by transformations of the EU’s borderlands, Lampedusa became the ‘empty signifier’ that “can travel to other locations in Europe, giving meaning to a variety of phenomena” (Horsti, 2023). Used both as a warning in the narratives of populists (‘we do not want to be another Lampedusa’), or as a diagnosis in the critiques of the EU’s policies (‘the EU is enlarged Lampedusa: a cemetery for migrants’), the memory of what happened to the island during the peak of the ‘migrant crisis’ still haunts Europe. Horsti perceives Europe from the perspective of the afterlives of disaster: as a borderland haunted by the demands of justice by those who survived it and those who were its victims. The practices of remembering disaster designate another one borderlands’ perception of Europe.

From what has been already said, it follows that the proliferation and blurring of borderlands make it challenging to represent them. The crisis of narration or representation of borderlands is discussed as one of the consequences of the European ‘migrant crisis’. How to perceive reality and narrate it from the perspective of de-territorialised and amorphous borderlands? The crisis of representation allows us to come back to the motif of borderlands as a site of transgression of identity. The recent study on cultural and literary narratives on borders and borderlands, edited by Pine and Konidari (2021), considers borderlander as an outcast narrator, preoccupied with differences and writing from no man’s land. Inhabiting the unhomely spaces of borderland, threshold, or exile, the borderlander become able to transgress identities and translate between idioms, without erasing them. In the next subsections, we will discuss how these kinds of transgressions and translations are possible in the everyday life of borderlanders and their practices of border activism.

2.2. De/Re/Bordering practices - borderwork – border regimes vs. everyday life

While the European ‘migrant crisis’ has had the impact of the re-bordering of borderlands and reconstructions of border regimes, the everyday life of borderlanders is not a simple by-product of these tendencies. It has its own rationale which is not reducible to border governance. In

this sub-section, we would like to examine how everyday life close to the border and over the border contributes to re/de-bordering practices. Following Deleixhe, Dembińska, and Iglesias (2021), we notice that even in securitised borderlands which are governed according to the needs of manifesting state power and blocking unwanted intrusions, borders remain messy and Janus-faced: “globalisation has not erased borders but it has recrafted their functions and turned them into key political instruments to police irregular and clandestine transnational activities. This redefinition of the core tasks of borders has led to a selective process of de-bordering and re-bordering. Though some transnational flows have been greatly facilitated, others have been put under heightened scrutiny and monitoring, leading to their securitisation. This new and complex situation created unprecedented social environments that are *securitised borderlands*”.

We are interested in the workings of ‘border culture’ in these securitised borderlands. Border culture is a culture “imagined and produced at boundaries, and in an increasing array of sites where visions, values, identities and other facets of human distinction meet and increasingly collide” (Konrad and Szary 2023, x). At the same time, we follow Konrad and Szary (2023, xi) in their postulate that we should try to avoid the ‘border culture trap’, according to which ‘culture is reduced to something that expresses otherness vis à vis mainstream, majority and/or ruling societies’. The essentialised vision of ‘border culture’ as something which always remains minoritarian, eccentric, and opposite to re-bordering, is based on one-sided wishful thinking which reduces the complexity and ambivalence of culture in the borderlands. The cited authors argue that we should understand border culture in a non-essentialist way which lets us see borderlands as areas “which defy unambiguous definition or categorisation” (Konrad and Szary 2023, xi). The unenclosed and vibrant character of border cultures finds many expressions. Konrad and Szary recall here very diverse examples drawn not only from Europe: “place-making practices of Lhotsampa refugees in Halifax, Canada, separations and intersec-tions of Afghanistan’s many ethno-linguistic areas, cultural expression and art at border cities, mental maps of borderlanders, the performance of border guards at the Wagah border where India and Pakistan meet, and the complex border-transcending geographies of the Akwesasne Mohawk Territory” (Konrad and Szary 2023, xi). They associate border culture with the decolonial concept of ‘border thinking’, defined as a way of seeing the world and social reality from the vantage point of being at *and amidst* social, cultural, and political borders; here, diversity, the co-existence of many different social worlds, and the daily negotiation of border-crossing rituals are the norm’ (Konrad and Szary 2023, xii). They also recognise the inherently political character of border thinking as a stance that is contrary to the populist bordering of Us/Them: “Border thinking counters the fiction of immutable border realities, meanings, and identities that is a source of misunderstandings of borders but also populist appropriations of them in terms of ‘taking back control’” (Konrad and Szary 2023, xii).

There are many possible concrete understandings of border culture in the new European borderlands. We can mention here, among others, borderland counter-topographies – examined by Kühnemund (2018) - who claims that one of the sources of the ‘migration crisis’ discourse is visual. We see migrants, illegality, and the crisis itself in a very simplified, repetitive, securitised, and spectacular way which blocks alternative representations: “The majority of the images illustrate migration and flight as dramas that, however, draw on well-known figures, icons, and metaphors: the victim, the threat, the refugee, the ‘waves’, ‘floods’ and ‘swarms’ of people, illegal acts of border-crossing and of smuggling, the fence, the boat, Lampedusa, the sea. Seen it before. They tell the old tale of ‘Us’ and ‘Them’ – they know their ‘Other’ very well.

They leave no questions, no doubt; they homogenise and victimise – and, above all, they emotionalise’ (Kühnemund 2018, 8-9). However, according to the author, other forms of visibility and recognition of undocumented migrants and borderlands are possible, and they are offered by documentary movies. Kühnemund (2018, 262) mobilises the concept of ‘Borderland Schengen’ as a counter-topographical space – his study offers the overview of a stubborn practice of documentary filmmaking with the ground to investigate European borderlands as contact zones composed of sites where a complex web of articulations and demands is not only expressed but also negotiated and contested’.

Border culture in the new European borderlands took also the form of hospitality or spaces of refuge. Turam (2021, 756) writes that about cities that refuse to play the role in the securitisation of borderlands: “Some gateway cities took on a new role of refugee protection and accommodation. These ‘cities of refuge’ created safe havens for refugees while resisting Europe’s fear-inducing anti-immigrant regime and rising xenophobia”. Turam argues that such cities were not content with offering apolitical humanitarian support, but – on the contrary – they became political agoras, opened for political subjectivisation of people on the move. Thus, their everyday life was far from apolitical and ordinary – it was rather politicised from the bottom up, providing resistance towards re-borderings. Squire (2020) supplements this viewpoint with her research on groups that challenged the normalisation of death and vulnerability in the European borderlands. She recalls such collective practices as welcome initiatives in humanitarian corridors, cemetery activism (dressing of migrants’ graves), or Sea-Watch rescue initiative as examples of lived experiences of people on the move and their allies in offering ‘dignity in motion’. Once again, everyday life of borderlanders provided the dynamics of border culture which challenged top-down securitisation.

The ordinary and embodied character of such borderlands’ infrastructures of solidarity was stressed in the research of Markodimitrakis (2021) on Greek cities with a case study of Crete. The author argues that neighbourhood communities have been critical in covering systemic deficiencies, and their support was - out of necessity – temporary and precarious. The rising precarisation of borderlands is thus one of the consequences of a securitised response to the ‘migration crisis’. It has been recognised also about the new precarious mobility economies in the borderlands that arose along the routes of migration. Achtnich (2023) argues in the study of these mobility economies that the figures of migrants as illegals, criminals, victims or threats cover the economic significance of migrant labor power, but also migrant’s bioeconomy and extraction of their mobility in new forms of transgoverning of migration. From this viewpoint, the everyday precarious life of migrants could be captured and exploited by economic actors.

The same tension between the extractive logic of border regimes and unsubordinated mobility is discussed by Chouliaraki and Georgiou (2022) in their research on the rise of digital borders. Digital circuits, functioning both in the ‘outer borders’ and ‘inner borders’ of Europe, mediate in procedures of bordering, aiming at capturing the mobility of migrants, but they are also contested by alternative uses of digital technology: “the border’s two imperatives, to national sovereignty and the biopolitical care for migrants, mix, and fuse in ways that primarily safeguard national and European integrity over migrant lives but also, in the process, carve out contingent and fragile spaces of care and solidarity for them’ (2022, 53). Digitalised borderlands thus became the spaces of digital control, governance and producing mediated invisibility of migrants, but they also help to recognise the condition of ‘throwntogetherness’ and organise ‘networked commons’, defined by the authors as ‘fragile but lively collectivities of

communication, collaboration, and self-expression between urban citizens and noncitizens that challenge the normative contours of the border” (2022, 24).

In the outer borderlands, this normative corrective power of Europe is related to the efforts to create integrated neighbourhoods. Del Sarto (2021) analyses how Europe transformed its forms of dominance over its borderlands in the Mediterranean Middle East and North Africa from former colonial enterprises to the current ‘Normative Europe Empire’. According to the author, the influence of the EU on its borderlands is more complicated than is suggested by the figure of ‘Fortress Europe’. The EU is interested in more than just controlling the movements of people. It uses its soft power to influence the reconstructions of its borderlands which serve its own needs. Rather than promoting democracy, human rights, and prosperity – the so-called ‘European values’ - the EU is not determined to support Europeanisation, but rather to create its subservient borderlands as neighbourhoods: secure, stable, and offering good business opportunities. Thus, the securitisation of borderlands should be seen only as a part of a wider process of making borderlands profitable and beneficial for the EU.

The extraction of everyday life of borderlanders’ is made possible by the development of what Dijstelbloem (2021) called ‘borders as infrastructures’, or ‘technopolitics of border controls’. The author argues that border studies must resist the trap of ‘borderism’, that is a reduction of its focus on territorial lines and official borders. One of the most overlooked forms of the restructuring of borderlands is a technological one. Borders became mobile vehicles, elastic in their localisation and workings. Technopolitics of the border rests on its ‘peramorphic’ characteristics (*peras* is the Greek word for boundary, limit, or end; and *morphic* originates from the Greek *morphe*, meaning shape or form). In practice, it means that almost everything that is not a border can become one through technological transformation: from digital databases, through vehicles, to laws and public services. Thus, technological peramorphic bordering exploits the everyday life of borderlands.

2.3. Border activism

Border activism is a more self-aware, purposeful effort that arises over the everyday life of borderlands and uses border as some point of reference: issue, site of action, weapon, or symbol. From its beginnings, border activism tended to treat borders as an object of transgression and transborder action (Laqua, 2023). But especially in the context of the ‘migrant crisis’ discourse, we should be attentive to how borders became an issue and a resource in both debordering and re-bordering activism. For example, Naples and Mendez (2015, 11) discuss how “re-bordering processes crystallise in regions where military techniques and detection strategies, and technologies of surveillance engineered for war have been put to the service of border enforcement”. In these cases, non-state, voluntary, and bottom-up involvement in re-bordering became a powerful scenario: “In this context military logics for resolving conflict and solving social problems have been applied to border enforcement, extending it beyond the purview of the state to include nonstate actors. For example, in Israel’s Modi’in area, Border Police trains youth to assist them in enforcing security measures and apprehending ‘illegal aliens’, while in the United States the Explorers programme, a subsidiary of the Boy Scouts of America, partners with Border Patrol to train young people “in skills used to confront terrorism, illegal immigration and escalating border violence”. From nativist groups like the Minutemen in the United States to white supremacy groups in Australia and extreme

nationalists in Europe, such extraofficial, border-enforcement initiatives aim to strengthen and reinforce the boundaries and lines that purportedly safeguard a nation, people, or way of life, as well as a set of corresponding moral codes' (2015, 11).

In the case of Europe, we might recall various recent examples of re-bordering activism, from everyday racism, segregation, and local policies analysed by Tyerman (2022) in France and the UK, through the creation of hostile environments – often in marginalised and working-class districts - based on the embodied exclusion of migrants (Vickers, 2019), to the rise of transnational networks of right-wing activists (Beck and Beck, 2022; Volk, 2019). These activities can be understood as attempts to provide social legitimisation and reinforcement of the European 'migration crisis' discourse, also because the far right and national populists adopted as their political narratives the imagery of fortress Europe, a nation under siege, borders under pressure, and uncontrolled migration. The discourse of securitisation made it also easier for populists to use borders as entities of purifying the image of the people from strangers (Lamour and Varga 2020) and ruling in the populist mode of the security state of exception (Diaz-Barriga and Dorsey 2020).

But the innovative debordering activist practices were also the by-product of the 'migrant crisis'. Della Porta (2018) summarises - the study on solidarity mobilisations during the crisis – that the very movements of migrants should be understood as 'acts of citizenship', or the claims to be included in the realm of the people. The practices of the groups who supported migrants in their efforts are named – in turn - as acts of solidarity. The activist repertoire by migrants and solidarity mobilisation was very rich and diverse. They addressed various kinds of borderings, proving that activists had the knowledge and recognition of the new cartography of European borderlands (civil disobedience, occupations of public buildings, chained protests, demonstrations against evictions, quiet/invisible and official/public encroachments to appropriate movement and its infrastructures, destroying identity documents, creation of makeshift communities and radical camps). These mobilisations make up the resource for further activism which Grappi (2021) calls a memory of migrant struggles contributing to articulating the new collective public beyond border regimes.

The phenomenon of 'citizen humanitarianism at the European borders' appeared during the crisis as the lived and embodied response to injustices and violence towards migrants. In their study of this phenomenon, Jumbert and Pascucci (2021) discuss how it de-professionalised and reclaimed humanitarianism for ordinary citizens, and how it was domesticated and institutionalised by them in everyday life. In some cases, citizen humanitarianism redefines and radicalises citizenship beyond the constraints of the nation-state population. Gonzales and Sigona (2017, 6) specify how borders act as permeable and fuzzy spaces in which seemingly stable and naturalised categories of citizenship, the people or inside are put into doubt, contributing to building political communities and ties beyond citizenship. Tazzioli and Walters (2019) add to this that though acts of solidarity became criminalised in the course of the 'migrant crisis' as 'crimes of solidarity', nevertheless, the repressions of citizens involved in these campaigns contribute even more to the challenging of the limits of European solidarity.

One of the main dilemmas of addressing these limits, faced by debordering activism, is posed by King (2016, 20): "How to navigate between autonomous practices that seek to escape the state, and representational practices that seek to transform it?". Or, in other words, it is a dilemma between reformism of public institutions (such as citizenship), and affirmation of autonomous action, often in an informal way and in everyday life. King specifies that migration

activism often does not take the form of collective action in the public view, but it is focused on effective escape from the mechanisms of power and control. For example, this dilemma between formal and informal practices is discussed by Marino (2021) concerning the novel phenomenon of digital solidarity: digital technologies which were identified as tools of surveillance, panopticism, and control, are sometimes reclaimed by migrant activists for their purposes, against the grain. The same dilemma could be detected in the case of mobile commoning in the Eastern borderlands of Poland and the EU: while the creation and maintenance of ties of solidarity with Ukrainian war refugees were accepted and even supported by Polish authorities, then the support for migrants used in proxy war by the Belarusian government was criminalised and had to develop in clandestine way (Moll, 2023). We should thus remain attentive to more visible and invisible forms of debordering activism.

Finally, one more important context entered and complicated the ‘migrant crisis’ discourse: the COVID-19 pandemic. The impact of the virus on borderlands and the reaction of its inhabitants are discussed in the next section. Here we would like to point out that besides the protests against border closures by transborder commuters or the anti-sanitary mobilisations against hygienic measures, part of the activism in the times of COVID-19 was devoted to solidarity with migrants. The spread of corona reinforced even more security-humanitarian narratives of saving lives which legitimise re-bordering: “The pandemic has been seized as an opportunity to strengthen existing deterrence measures and hamper migrants’ access to asylum through biopolitical and spatial tactics that aim to restructure the border regime” (Tazzioli and Stierl, 2021, 539). The narrative according to which ‘the ports are closed to protect refugees’ was rejected by the solidarity protests organised against hygienic borders. A case study from Germany demonstrates how temporary suspensions of the right to assembly in public spaces strengthen the proliferation of pro-migrant activism (Zajak, Stjepandić, and Steinhilper, 2021). Thus, the intersection of ‘migrant crisis’ and pandemics contributed to the development of border solidarity and activism during the times of COVID-19 (Wille and Weber, 2020). The following section will address how these developments have shaped borderlanders’ perceptions of Europe during pandemics.

3. Re-bordering during the Covid-19 pandemic shaping Borderlanders’ perceptions of Europe

The outbreak the Covid-19 pandemic in mid-March 2020 and the implementation of border restrictions on many EU internal borders has revealed the vulnerability of open borders and cross-border cooperation. The response to the pandemic was predominately national, undermining the imaginary of a borderless Europe in favour of a new discourse of ‘global nationalism’ (Bieber, 2020), an ‘era of post-globalisation’ (Konrad, 2021), the ‘advent of unilateralism’ (Böhm, 2021) or ‘covidfencing’ (Medeiros et al. 2021). The term ‘covidfencing’ specifically highlights the immediate nation states’ reactions to the pandemic in the form of border controls or temporary border closures – an extraordinary measure in the Schengen area, where it was described as “blocking and/or reversing the European integration process” (Medeiros et al. 2021, 96; Opiłowska and Weber, forthcoming). Moreover, as argued by Renner et.al. (2022, 826), in the need to find ways to reduce the pandemic risks, “European politics

witnessed a COVID-19-related backslide into patterns of nation–state-based problem solving, revealing once again, how modern society is spatially organised in a territorial form and how these structures do act as a blueprint in times of crisis.” Casaglia (2021) also points to this paradox of combating the virus through re-territorialisation and the role of borders as tools to defend ontological security. Casaglia emphasises that the effectiveness of measures would probably benefit from countries’ coordination and collaboration, as well as from the protection and care of those who are more vulnerable to the spread of the virus.

Despite many negative consequences, the pandemic related border crisis put borders to the forefront of research and public discours. This section discusses and summarises the scientific literature focused on the Covid-19 impact on borderlanders’ perception of Europe. It should be noted that this event from the very beginning attracted huge interest from border scholars (see Brunet-Jailly and Carpenter, 2020; Jańczak, 2020; Wille and Kanesu, 2020; Kenwick and Simmons, 2020; Wang, Zou and Liu, 2020; Novotný 2021; Kajta and Opiłowska, 2022; Opiłota and Böhm 2022; Prokkola and Andersen, 2021; Weber, Theis and Terrolion 2021; Lara-Valencia and Laine, 2022; Weber, 2022; Böhm et.al. 2023; Brodowski, Nesselhauf and Weber, 2023; Kajta and Opiłowska, 2023; Rudhuber et.al., 2023; Rogowski and Frąckowiak, 2023; Tarvet and Klatt, 2023). Although we have not identified any publication that would delve into the question of how the crisis shaped the European imaginary of border regions’ residents, it is worth looking at the research outputs analysing recent (re)bordering trends that have shaken the certainty of open borders as one of the bases of European integration.

3.1. First reactions to re-bordering

As many authors demonstrate, the restrictions on border crossings were introduced without any consultations with local and regional actors. Therefore, they came as a shock to local communities. What could be observed at the beginning of the pandemic was civil society engaging in performative activities that demonstrated solidarity with the neighbours and their trans-border belonging. Banners with slogans such as ‘We belong together’ or ‘United in heart and strong together. See you again’ were visible in public spaces of many border regions (Opiłowska, 2022; Wille, 2020).

In contrast to these acts of identification with Europe, some border region residents also expressed their support for border restrictions (Opiłowska, 2022; MOT, 2021; IPSOS, 2020). At the Hungarian-Romanian border, Hungarian citizens perceived the border as a protective barrier and framed Romanians as the source of possible infection (MOT, 2021). Also, in the Dutch-Belgian border region, the closing of the border was initially welcomed by Belgians. The mayor of Słubice – the sister city of Frankfurt (Oder) – at the beginning of the pandemic appealed to the voivode of Lubuskie to close the Polish-German border completely, justifying it by reference to the will of residents. Moreover, old historical resentments have been reinforced and acts of discrimination have been reported. According to the MOT report (2021, 98), German citizens in the region bordering Alsace and Moselle perceived the borders as a ‘bulwark against the spread of the virus’. At the French-German border, where cross-border cooperation started to develop already in the 1950s, nationalist and xenophobic resentments emerged and stereotypes that were thought to have been overcome were suddenly reawakened (Roth 2021, p. 40).

It is worth noting that the European reference did not only mean the prominence of European integration. Casaglia et.al. (2020, 2) stressed that the pandemic also changed the populist discourses from anti-EU positions to complaints about “the lack of EU cooperation in coping with the epidemic, exploiting this lack of transnational solidarity in a fierce new criticism of European elites.” Certainly, it can be argued that re-bordering policies evoked ambiguous reactions of citizens in many border regions. Apart from expressions of cross-border solidarity and of organising protests against the restrictions, some voices in favour of border closures, including the imaginary of a secure, bounded nation-state and of borders as protective barriers against threats from the outside could be identified (Kajta and Opiłowska, 2023). These incidents have challenged the imaginary on borderlands as places of reconciliation and European integration.

3.2. Protests and lobbying

The crisis situation and the political decision to introduce border restrictions revealed the weakness of local and regional governance structures vis-à-vis state authorities. However, it has also mobilised stakeholders in border regions to be more active and visible on the national and international arena to safeguard their interests. Hence, cross-border cooperation and transnational practices have been perceived and depicted in a European perspective. Many publications point out that in their appeals to national authorities, they stressed transborder integration of communities and the unity of Europe. Luxembourg’s Foreign Minister emphasised that Germans, French and Luxembourgers have all grown up together on the borders and instead of seeing borders, they see bridges (Wörner, 2020, n.p.). The Federation of Polish Euroregions underlined daily contacts and living in symbiosis (Wyborcza, 2020). Thus, Europe without borders has been framed as a common achievement (Kajta and Opiłowska, 2023).

It was the cross-border commuters whose lives were most affected by the border closures, so they became very active in protesting against the restrictions (Novotný, 2021; Novotný and Böhm, 2022). Together with border region residents they pointed out the uniqueness of borderlands and organised demonstration demanding a re-opening of borders (Cyrus and Ulrich, 2020). It is worth noting that references to Europe were widely used during these performative events. In Frankfurt (Oder) and Słubice, the protesters organised the action under the slogan ‘Less fear, more Europe’ and sang the EU anthem *Ode to Joy* (Horbach, 2020). They emphasised their belonging to united Europe: “*We have long been united in Europe, which is particularly evident here on the Polish-German border, where people live and work across divisions and national borders.*” (Horbach, 2020, n.p.; Opiłowska, 2022). Similar activities in public spaces took place at the German-French border. In May 2020 activists from the Young European Federalists Association removed the barriers at two border crossings in Saarland and sprayed ‘#DontTouch-MySchengen’ onto the asphalt (Wille, 2020, 15). Hence, it can be argued that the crisis on the one hand has shaken the certainty of open borders in Europe, but on the other hand made European values more internalised and thus motivated borderlanders to demonstrate their European affiliation. This confirms the study conducted by Renner et al. (2022, 838). By analysing German media coverage on the pandemic consequences in the German-Polish borderland they identify a discourse strand pointing to

“the everyday relevance of European integration for border region residents and cross-border economy as well as the (symbolic) significance of this border for the process of Europeanisation”. Are borderlands, then, laboratories of European integration according to the macro-narrative of EU institutions? This question will be addressed in the next section.

3.3. Borderlands as living labs of European integration?

The Covid-19 pandemic put to the test cross-border cooperation and governance structures such as Euroregions, twin cities and EGTCs. Many authors analysed this challenge by applying the resilience concept (Böhm et.al., 2023; Jagetic Andersen and Prokkola, 2022; Opiłowska, 2022, 2023; Opiłowska and Weber, forthcoming). As discussed in the previous sections, the crisis made both institutional actors and residents aware that open borders in Europe cannot be taken for granted and constitute a value to be cared for and nurtured. Therefore, local institutions responded very quickly to the challenge and implemented adaptation mechanisms. In the first phase of the pandemic, they focused on providing solid information and maintaining transborder cooperation to mitigate uncertainty and fear among residents. Special Covid-19 hotlines, Infobest, Frontaliers Grand Est, CEC, MOSA, Maison du Luxembourg have been set up to inform about the changing regulations (MOT, 2021). Coordination meetings between stakeholders were moved to online mode because of the mobility restrictions. It is worth noting that thanks to experience in cooperation, mutual trust and established cross-border structures, the institutionalised structures quickly assumed leadership in managing the crisis (Kajta and Opiłowska, 2022; Opiłowska and Böhm, 2022; Weber et al., 2021; MOT, 2021).

Local actors also recognised the need to further strengthen the cross-border instruments, as was expressed in many strategic documents. They claimed that the decisions made by state authorities had a negative impact on the daily lives of border region residents and threatened the existing achievements of the European integration process, while also challenging them to raise cross-border cooperation to a new level to make it more resistant to future crises.

By acting together border regions increased their capacities and agency. Some examples provided by the European Commission (COM 2021/393) illustrate the joint actions: the Greater Region created a Pandemic Task Force to coordinate pandemic management, Görlitz and Zgorzelec run joint emergency exercises; the EGTC - The Bánát Triplex Confinium delivered face masks and hand sanitisers from Hungary to Romanian authorities, the Südtirol region sent protective equipment to the autonomous provinces of Bolzano and Trentino; hospitals in the Tyrolean towns took care of Italian patients.

As in the above outlined case of border activism within the ‘migration crisis’, acts of protests, demonstrations, lobby actions and appeals of border regions have been also performed during the pandemic. They reached not only decision-makers at national level, but also political actors at the European level where the negative consequences of border closures and restrictions have been recognised and some countermeasures have been implemented. The European Commission opened ‘green corridors’ for the transit of essential goods and issued guidelines on the free movement of workers and emergency assistance in cross-border healthcare (COM 2021/393). Moreover, the Council of the European Union issued recommendations (EU, 2020/1475; EU, 2021/119), to provide special provisions for residents who cross the border frequently to work, school or for family reasons. The EC revised also the in 2017 adopted

communication ‘Boosting Growth and Cohesion in EU Border Regions’ (COM, 2017/534) to adjust the action plan to the post-Covid-19 reality. In these documents issued at the EU level, the uniqueness of border regions is emphasised and the need to afford them special regulations that regard the transnational practices of borderlanders. Whether this crisis will transform and strengthen the power of cross-border actors and awaken a new enthusiasm for deepening European integration to prevent similar crises in the future, or on the contrary, fuel the nationalist sentiments and deepen insecurities, requires further research and observation. Thus, B-SHAPES will examine how the Covid-19 crisis impacted the borderlanders’ narratives on borders and their perception of Europe. Along with the two determinants of borderlanders’ perception of Europe delineated above, European elections trigger debates about the vision of the European project and influence the attitudes of citizens, including those living on the border. In view of this, section 3 will recapitulate the most important findings from academic research.

4. European elections – political groups in European Parliament and their perception of re/de-bordering

Taking the approaches to borderlanders’ perceptions of Europe that were outlined above into consideration, it can be argued that the programmes of the political groups in the European Parliament demonstrate divergent visions of Europe. Indeed, the reflections at the level of the representatives of the Member States in the EU institutions do not deal with ideas about Europe’s borders, their perception by citizens or the role they play in this context. Rather, European parties regard border issues in the context of securitising borders as a means of ensuring European stability. As Osuna (2022) argues, at the same time external borders are becoming a tool for populist parties to encircle themselves from others and demarcate ‘us’ from ‘them’. For the the four populist and Eurosceptic parties that Osuna covered, ‘border’ is predominantly perceived as the external borders of the EU, and only to a lesser extent as the internal borders between the member states. This leads to a politicisation of border security. Such parties’ manifestos, as well as government actions, can also contribute to a growing sense of fear or even panic among Europeans (Vollmer, 2019). Although the issue of border protection has always been an area of interest for each national state, the European integration process has made it necessary for the Member States to internationalise the protection of both their internal borders and those of the European Union. It can be observed that as a result of the increasing mobility of people, following the 2004 and 2007 enlargement of the European Union (D’Auria, McMorrow, Pichelmann, 2008), as well as the Schengen agreement, the issue of border protection and migration has become extremely important, going beyond the framework of traditional border security and its previous definition. It should be emphasised that both protection and borders can also be found in the legal acts establishing the EU, above all in Article 77 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union with regard to co-decision by the Parliament and the Council on the form of visa and migration policy as well as certain principles concerning its procedure.

The development of common policies in this field also refers directly to the general principles of the European Union, in particular to the principle of solidarity. The need for cooperation and

coordination is intended to foster effective protection of the borders of the entire Union. This solidarity, however, is not just a legal provision, but a response to real regional challenges faced by the European Union. External conflicts, humanitarian crises, climate change and poverty are factors which in recent years have implied migration to Europe. As argued by Carrera (2019) policy fields such as security, combating terrorism and cross-border crime such as human and drug trafficking also require from member states to jointly monitor and control borders to ensure security both within each country and for the European Union as a whole.

Nevertheless, a common migration and border protection policy has become fundamental to the European integration process. The aim of harmonising standards and a common approach to border management is an important step towards building a single area of freedom, security and justice in the European Union, while at the same time effective border protection is an important factor in creating and enhancing citizens' confidence in the EU institutions and the member states themselves by strengthening the sense of security and stability in society (Kriesi et al., 2021). In addition to the obvious above-mentioned advantages of having a common border policy within the EU (security, more efficient migration management, stability), it is also worth adding that coordinated border protection also contributes to safeguarding the economic interests of the EU by preventing illegal smuggling of goods. This goal is to maintain fair competition in the EU single market and to ensure consumer safety.

Recent crises as outlined in the previous sub-chapters, have moved borders into the spotlight of national political discourses as well as the European public sphere. The issues as 'migration crisis', re-bordering trends during the Covid-19 pandemic, a humanitarian crisis on the EU external border between Belarus and Poland/Baltic States and finally Ukrainians seeking refuge in the EU following Russia's invasion on Ukraine, put border protection at the centre of consideration and discussion on the EU level, in particular by the Council and the Parliament. This is reflected both in the agenda created by the various political groups in the European Parliament (bringing together parties from different European countries with similar ideological and political outlooks) and in the votes and resolutions which have taken place in recent years, and which have directly dealt with border issues. What we may see is that the perception of border by the European parties is closer to a neo-functionalist approach to understanding the control of European borders (Ozan, 2021) and does not address the cross-border and social dimension of borders or the border as a cultural bridge. The following section highlights how re/de-bordering is reflected in the programmes of political groups sitting in the European Parliament.

4.1. The issue of re/de-bordering in the official programmes of political groups in the European Parliament

It should be noted at the outset of this overview, that scientific analyses of how political factions approach borders of Europe are rare to find. This may be due, on the one hand, to the scarcity of space devoted to this issue in official political programmes, but, on the other hand, to the dynamic atmosphere accompanying negotiations on borders, their understanding and security in the European Parliament in recent years. The essence of the problem, which is the issue of EU and national borders, has made it necessary for political groups in the European Parliament to include this issue at least minimally in their party programmes. Nevertheless, for the purpose of B-SHAPES it is important to get insights from the analysis of parties'

programmes. The **European People's Party (EPP)** has made the issue of border protection one of the four main pillars of its programme called a 'European Security Pact', which consists of three elements: protecting, creating and strengthening. The fundamental link between all elements of this agenda is a strong conviction of the need for increased control and protection of the Union's internal and external borders. To achieve this, the EPP proposes, among other things, to strengthen the powers of Europol and to transform it into 'Eurocops', a fully operational and autonomous police agency responsible for fighting terrorism, corruption, and cross-border crime such as drug and arms smuggling. At the same time, this political group envisages strengthening the possibilities offered by the European arrest warrant. The EPP also wants to see the creation of EU bodies responsible for an integrated EU approach to crisis management coordinating civilian and military missions and operations. The pillar named protecting, which is crucial from the point of view of bordering, concerns above all the belief in simultaneously building physical infrastructure to block access to the European Union at its external borders, but also signing agreements and arrangements with neighbouring countries such as Tunisia and Morocco.

Frontex is intended by the European People's Party to become a more effective tool for protecting the so-called New Pact on Migration and Asylum. The EPP also wants to see the establishment of a European Security Council made up of Member State ministers responsible for internal and external security, which is to be set up in response to the urgent need to develop an integrated approach to dealing with conflict and crises at the EU's borders. There are no other references in the party's official programme to border issues, including the reinstatement of possible border controls. Thus, the EPP focuses in its programme on the external borders of the EU, while internal issues are of no interest to the EPP (apart from the context related to the protection of the internal market and the flow of migrants, which is to be controlled through, for example, the aforementioned Eurocops mandate).

The Left in the European Parliament (formerly known as GUE/NGL) does not have extensive program proposals on its websites, and its founding declarations are not fully up to date due to their age (over 30 years). One of the few hinted-at points in their programme (Peace and Solidarity) states that 'foreign and security strategies must be based on peace, as opposed to the current militarisation trend'.

On the other hand, it can be observed that this is reflected in the casual publications posted on the website by the Left. For example, last year representatives of this party posted publications criticising the 'New Migration Pact' (acknowledging that 'the Pact reinforces current failed policies and practices by focusing on deterrence, containment of people fleeing third countries, strengthening external borders, detention, and acceleration of procedures at the expense of the individual right to asylum') and a separate pamphlet criticising the erection of borders at the EU's external borders, recognising that 'masked by the mantra of effectiveness and efficiency, the European Council and Commission continue to normalise and validate the xenophobic narrative of the far right, posing a serious threat to fundamental human rights such as the right to asylum'.

Also, the other left-wing group in the Europarliament, **the Socialists and Democrats**, does not have many references to the topic of borders in its programme. One of the pillars of the organisation's priorities on its website is called 'open strategic autonomy', which vaguely indicates the need to lay the foundations for a common foreign policy. This kind of approach is supposed to ensure that Europe remains self-sufficient and less vulnerable to external shocks.

A bit more news is provided by the full S&D strategy on security, under the name of open strategic autonomy. In this document, however, one looks in vain for references to the issue of European borders. At the same time, the security issue is limited mainly to the military aspect, the coordination of armaments policy in the Member States and the strengthening of cooperation within NATO. As with the previous political group in the Euro-parliament, the S&Ds also call for agreements with the EU's neighbours to ensure stability within the organisation, while not specifying the scope of possible agreements.

A centrist and liberal political group advocating for progressive policies, **Renew Europe**, devoted an exceptionally large amount of space in its programme to border issues. We can find many policy papers on their website, which are written by representatives of the various parties, as well as by the Renew Europe board and its staff. Although there is only one mention of the dangers facing Europe's borders in the Charter establishing the organisation, however, a lot of space is also devoted to this issue in the list of priorities for the current term of the European Parliament.

An examination of Renew Europe's stance on border issues reveals a multifaceted approach that emphasises both security and humanitarian concerns. The group recognises the importance of secure borders in maintaining security and order within the EU. They are likely to advocate robust border control measures to prevent illegal activities such as trafficking and terrorism, while ensuring the integrity of the EU's external borders. Renew Europe's position on border issues also reflects a commitment to upholding human rights and promoting solidarity. They are likely to support measures to manage migratory flows fairly and humanely, possibly advocating a comprehensive and compassionate immigration policy. This could include provisions for asylum seekers and refugees, as well as efforts to address the root causes of migration through international cooperation and development aid. In addition, the importance of a coordinated and cooperative approach to border management is likely to be emphasised. They may also advocate to 'encourage all relevant actors to strengthen and speed up the implementation and deployment of the European Border and Coast Guard, in a more ambitious way, to reinforce the EU's external borders, which is a precondition for a well-functioning Schengen area'.

The Greens/EFA, in their vision of Europe state explicitly that 'by 2024, we want the European Union to have moved away from 'fortress Europe' towards a continent of sanctuary, able to welcome people in dignified and humane conditions, and to treat everyone as full citizens. This will require putting in place solidarity mechanisms to welcome asylum seekers and migrants, safeguarding their rights, and reversing EU action in the world that creates the conditions that force people to leave their homes'. Although this statement does not contain any specific policies, it is the only one to recognise 'fortifying' Europe as a wrong approach to defending its perceived values. Nevertheless, the numerous position papers produced by the group have an emphasis on signing effective agreements with countries neighbouring with the EU to protect borders and a call for incentivising more cross-border cooperation.

For the two smaller political groups in the Euro-Parliament, in turn, border and boundary issues are an extremely important point on their agenda. The groups share a conservative and Eurosceptic worldview and take the issue of external and internal security very seriously. The political group **European Conservatives and Reformists** places the protection of European citizens and borders at the top of their agenda (Safeguarding Citizens and Borders within 'Visions for Europe'), considering that border security means freedom for Europe's citizens

from threats of violence and criminal phenomena, which should be a priority for the European Union. The group also insists on improving the European Migration System and revising the existing system. The ECR recognises that existing tools are ineffective in combating contemporary phenomena of globalisation regional conflicts mass migration or poverty.

Representatives of this political formation call for greater support from the European Union to Member States to protect the Union's external borders and to limit the possibility of obtaining asylum status in the Union and the abuse of privileges associated with it. The ECR also intends to strengthen the role of FRONTEX in an unspecified way and to continue working with third countries to restrict the flow of migrants into the European Union. An interesting point raised by the ECR is that it also emphasises its involvement in the creation of a unified and publicly accessible database to control the movement of people, particularly within the Schengen area. The ECR also highlights the advantages of introducing Passenger Name Records, an agreement between member states which would oblige them to complete basic passenger information on European flights to prevent and detect crime and terrorism. Similarly, the ECR is keen to see the development of a European Criminal Records Information System to share information on criminals and suspects between EU law enforcement agencies, such as EUROJUST and EUROPOL.

Likewise, **The Identity and Democracy (ID)** group in the European Parliament within its Statute declares 'safeguarding the identity of the citizens and nations in Europe. The right to control, regulate and limit immigration is a fundamental principle shared by the members of the group. So is their willingness to fight for a safer Europe with well- protected external borders and a stronger cooperation to tackle terrorism and islamisation'. This political group also assumes that the Republic of Turkey will not be allowed to join the European Union. The programme proposals presented are interesting in this sense, that this conservative political group is the only one to link the border issue with the cultural and religious dimension of the border problem. The declaration of disagreement with the so-called 'islamisation of Europe' shows that borders are understood here as religious barriers between implicitly Christian Europe and the Islamic Middle East or North Africa. At the same time, borders are understood as barriers separating Europeans from criminal threats. Secure borders and a strong European Union are supposed to ensure the security of all Europeans. In its statute, ID also adds that one of its priorities for the forthcoming term of the European Parliament is to protect the EU's external borders as 'every nation has the right to protect, control and supervise its own borders. The EU should focus more on the effective returning of illegal and criminal immigrants to their countries of origin'. This demonstrates the belief that the issue of border protection remains a national issue and that Member States are entitled to freely develop their own policies in this field, with their national interests at the forefront. The vision of Europe and its borders is not only part of debates within EU institutions, but triggers also public discussions, in particular during European elections. Hence, the next section outlines how re/de-bordering have been framed during the elections in 2019.

4.2. Re-/de-bordering in past European elections (2019)

The 2019 European Parliament elections were the first after the 'migration crisis' in 2015. Although the peak of citizens' interest in migration issues came rather at a time when they could see daily images of groups of refugees at the EU's external borders, such as in Hungary

at the border with Serbia or train stations in Austria and Germany, the issue of migration and the borders of the Union continued to be important in the following years (Braun, Schäfer, 2022; Lutz, Karstens, 2021). But also, the Brexit referendum in 2016 turned the question of the future character of the EU-UK border, especially regarding the specific situation of Northern Ireland, into a yet unresolved, pan-European topic. Reports of migrants reaching Europe via the Mediterranean in improvised boats, photos and videos of migrants in boats being rescued by volunteers and navy ships were a reminder of the continuing migration into Europe had an impact on voters' decisions (van der Brug, Gattermann, de Vreese, 2022). Emotions were aroused, for example, by footage from Calais in France or the African exclaves belonging to Spain, where migrants and refugees tried to get through the physical barriers to the other side.

In countries such as Italy and France, the issue of border control has become a central point of debate. The Italian government, led by Matteo Salvini, leader of the Northern League, has used anti-immigration rhetoric, calling for tougher measures against migrants and criticising EU migration policy. In a similar vein, French President Emmanuel Macron has sought to strengthen European cooperation on migration management, while seeking to secure France's borders against an uncontrolled 'influx of migrants'.

However, in some countries, such as Germany and Spain, the border issue has been treated more as part of a broader debate on the future of the European Union. Parties such as the CDU in Germany and the PSOE in Spain emphasised the importance of European cooperation in border protection as a key element in preserving unity and stability in Europe. In addition, as some studies demonstrate, some populist and Eurosceptic parties, such as the Brexit Party in the UK and the Alternative for Germany (AfD) in Germany, used the topic of borders as a tool to undermine the authority of the European Union and promote their anti-integration agenda (Dennison, Geddes, 2019).

In Poland, the ruling party Law and Justice (PiS) focused on border security issues, both in the context of migration and security threats. PiS advocated tighter border controls and opposed EU plans for refugee relocation, which was supported by a large part of the Polish population. Hungary, under Viktor Orbán, also focused on the topic of borders in the context of migration management. The Hungarian government continued to build a border fence to stop migrants, which became a key element of their national security strategy. In the Baltic States, such as Estonia, Latvia and Lithuania, the topic of borders was closely linked to security in the context of Russia's aggressive actions. Political parties in these countries often emphasised the need to strengthen EU support for border protection and defence against potential external threats, but they were not directly concerned with the issue of economic migration, as newcomers to Europe tended to settle in the richer and more socially diverse countries of Western Europe.

To conclude, the European parties differed in their approach towards migration policy and border issues. Their view on the internal and external borders was a result of both the domestic political affairs and the ongoing events in Europe (Abou-Chadi, Green-Pedersen, Mortensen, 2020). All in all, they referred to a broad spectrum of issues such as migration control, border security, national sovereignty, and European integration (Rios, 2019). We may see that populist parties and political groups tended to use the border theme as a tool to mobilise the electorate through anti-immigration rhetoric and calls for tighter border controls throughout the last years (Hobolt, de Vries, 2016). On the other hand, pro-European parties emphasised the need for cooperation in border management within the European Union and the need for openness

and solidarity towards migrants. In a country where the issue of migration was particularly heated, such as Italy, France or Germany, the topic of borders was important in the public discussion and influenced the voters' choice (Coleman, 2019). Ultimately, while the topic of borders was not the only one, it was certainly one of the key issues that shaped the discussion and electoral decisions during the 2019 European Parliament elections and continues to be an important topic in the political arena (Hankinson, 2024).

4.3. The issue of re/de-bordering in EP's votes and statements

During the 2019 - 2024 parliamentary term, the European Parliament took several important decisions in the form of votes that had to do with border issues and could affect their current and future meaning for Europeans and migrants arriving from outside. It should be pointed out that border issues have become extremely important to the various political parties, which, however, has not prevented them from cooperating and reaching a common position on the issue. For example, in the proceedings before the European Parliament (2021/0394 (COD)) on the Digitalisation of cross-border judicial cooperation, members of all political parties present in the EU Parliament supported the proposals almost unanimously - 551 MEPs voted in favour of this law strengthening access to justice in cross-border civil, commercial, and criminal matters, with only 5 voting against. Also, the work in the European Parliament's committees on the expected and soon to be voted New Migration Pact was surprising in developing a consensus and harmonious approach.

However, there was a stronger polarisation of votes as early as May 2021, with the vote on Resolution 2020/2116(INI) concerning a resolution on human rights protection and the EU external migration policy. Although the proposal ultimately passed (the Parliament adopted it by 358 votes to 309, with 26 abstentions), there was no voting discipline within the political groups and the results were mixed. For example, the majority of EPP MEPs voted against shoulder-to-shoulder with ECR members, while a vast majority of the non-aligned MEPs supported the project. The resolution called for a sustainable and effective readmission process for returnees, ensuring compliance with human rights principles in all agreements with third countries. Additionally, it urged increased resettlement pledges and the establishment of safe and legal pathways for refugees, emphasising the nexus between human rights and migration in EU policies and dialogues with other countries.

More divergence could be seen at the micro level, in the work of the committees and the statements of the different political factions. For example, in April 2023, the EPP, as the largest political group, in its official statement posted on the website, criticised the left-wing political groups in parliament for “refusing to face the reality about the migration challenge in Europe today” and urged to that “there is no migration policy without border protection and controls. (...) If we want to show solidarity, then we must restore the order at our borders, if needed by building fences where they are needed”.

In a statement after the summit in March 2023, the EPP declared that “Europe should maintain its openness to the world while concurrently safeguarding its borders”, recognising that the protection of the external borders by FRONTEX prevents the smuggling of illegal goods and reduces the risk to life for those attempting to enter Europe. By the EPP, this approach allows effective control of the EU's external borders, as well as prevents neighbouring countries from

using migrants as a bargaining chip against the Union. This political group in the same statement underlined the necessity to finalise the Pact on Asylum and Migration and find a solution that was co-authored by its representatives.

Other groups in the European Parliament also frequently speak out on border issues, most of which relate to EU foreign policy and the signing of agreements with third countries, especially in the Northern Africa, around which there is virtually unanimity. These topics are often raised by the Renew Europe group, for example. For example, in its statements of November 2023 and February 2024, it addressed the following issues: collection and transfer of advance passenger information (API) and a deal on the reform of the Schengen Border Code prepared to govern the controls at the EU's internal and external borders.

When reflecting on the parties' programmes from the perspective of B-SHAPES assumptions, it can be argued that borders are perceived by the parties represented in the European Parliament mainly as fences. The main focus lies on the external borders. They shape a perception of separating the rich Europe from its poorer neighbours, a perception of borders as a tool to ensure security and stabilisation from threats caused, for example, by local conflicts. Whereas the conception of borders as a line dividing nations or cultures can be regarded as their common approach, they differ in defining ways how to secure the borders. While most parties support the idea of signing agreements with third countries to limit migration, some also advocate building physical barriers at the border (EPP), while the left parties focus on the humane treatment of those who stand at the threshold of Europe's borders. The most conservative group, ID, on the other hand, also refers to the concept of 'Fortress Europe' as a tightly knit security monolith that protects the EU's ability to decide who is allowed in. To a lesser extent, border narratives could also be interpreted as borders understood as gates. However, this opportunity is supposed to be exclusive, and Europe is free to choose those it welcomes on its doorstep. At the same time, there is a lack of reference to the positive dimension of the internal borders, a lack of emphasis on the role of the regional dimension of cross-border cooperation and the cultural exchanges that take place there.

The above presented summary of how the border is presented in EU documents, party programmes, and voting acts allows us to argue that it is predominately (except for the Left and the Greens/EFA) reflected from the neo-functionalist and security perspectives. 'Borderless Europe' is perceived as one of the pillars of the European integration project. Safeguarding this pillar requires re-bordering and militarisation of the external borders even at the expense of violations of human rights. Political parties have employed both migration and border themes to persuade voters to support their agendas. Especially Euroscepticism was used to frame argumentation strategies applied in political campaigns. Thus, the next section provides an overview of literature discussing Euroscepticism and its facets relevant for B-SHAPES project.

5. Euroscepticism and its cousins

Euroscepticism is intertwined with other social trends, ideologies, and frames for making sense of the social and political world. A number of scholars have established a link between Euroscepticism and populism (Rodrik, 2018; Leconte, 2010; Buti and Pichelmann, 2017; Dijkstra et al., 2020; Mazzoleni, 2023; Lamour and Varga, 2020). Populism, as a way of political parties or figures to present the world to ordinary people, has many different dimensions that

make the phenomenon difficult to define, but one dimension that seems to be common to all analyses of populism is its claim that there is a confrontation between a ‘pure’ people and a corrupt elite (Mudde, 2007; Akkerman et al., 2014). This anti-establishment view has strong parallels with Euroscepticism, as it is easy to cast the EU, ‘Brussels’ or ‘faceless bureaucrats’ as a remote elite that is out of touch with ordinary people (Dijkstra et al., 2020: 742). However, empirical analyses of party politics have shown that Euroscepticism and populism remain distinct, with Dijkstra et al. (2020) noting examples of Podemos as a populist party that is not very Eurosceptic or the British Conservatives that score low on populism but high on Euroscepticism: ‘The two issues are statistically correlated, but populism only ‘explains’ about half the variation in anti-EU voting’ (Dijkstra et al., 2020: 742). In other words, while Eurosceptic narratives are frequently used by populists, we must avoid a blanket conflation of the two terms.

Furthermore, popular attitudes towards the EU are part and parcel of more general world view that concerns the relative merits of open vs. closed borders, ‘de-bordering’ or ‘re-bordering’ (Popescu, 2012), the degree of openness towards immigration, and broader attitudes towards globalisation (cf. Kriesi, 2007; Kriesi et al., 2008). It has become commonplace to associate Euroscepticism with the ideological right, with nationalism and with a nativism that cherishes the state, the nation and control over borders (Mazzoleni, 2023). In fact, it would be difficult to identify far-right parties that are not also Eurosceptic. However, some Euroscepticism has also been detected on the left of the political spectrum, e.g. by British proponents of ‘Lexit’. However, while we can expect a blanket rejection of European integration from those on the radical right, we should anticipate more issue-specificity in their Euroscepticism from politicians on the far left (Kriesi, 2020; Lauener, 2023: 120).

Accordingly, Euroscepticism must be defined broadly as general as well as issue-specific critiques of European integration. Attitudes that go beyond a clear-cut ‘no to Europe’ have been captured through distinctions such as that between ‘hard’ and ‘soft’ Euroscepticism (Szczerbiak and Taggart, 2009) and that between instrumental and political Euroscepticism (Hobolt and Tilley, 2014; Lubbers and Scheepers, 2005). But Euroscepticism should also capture nuances such as opposition to specific policies like free movement in general (Lauener, 2023, Vasilopoulou and Talving, 2019; Lutz, 2021), or cross-border mobility in a particular region (Parker, 2013; Bürkner, 2020; Galgóczi and Leschke, 2015). It should also include disappointment with unfulfilled promises of European integration (Krasteva, 2020) and a perceived lack of sensitivity on the part of the EU to specific local needs (Durand et al., 2020).

5.1 Euroscepticism through regional variables

Euroscepticism varies not only in its content but also from country to country and over time (Leconte, 2010, 4). Indeed, analyses have shown large geographical variation between *and within* EU member states (Lubbers and Scheepers, 2005). In taking account of such local factors, the regional level of analysis has become increasingly prominent in the study of popular Euroscepticism. Rurality (Schoene, 2019) increases in unemployment (Lechler, 2019), distance from Brussels (Lubbers and Scheepers, 2007), share of tourism (Lubbers and Scheepers, 2007) and commuting (Lauener and Bernhard, 2023) have all been identified as influencing regional levels of Euroscepticism, but they have received less attention than economic decline. Regions in economic decline tend to have higher levels of Euroscepticism

(Dijkstra et al., 2020; Lipps and Schraff, 2021). What is more, this effect is dynamic, insofar as Euroscepticism has been shown to be higher in regions in decline, but this has been the case only since the launch of the single market (Mayne and Katsanidou, 2023, 752), which makes the EU an easy target for narratives about market liberalisation preceding, and potentially causing, economic decline.

Immigration rates have also been named as a key factor in driving regional rates of Euroscepticism. Here the picture is less clear-cut. For example, Dijkstra et al. (2020) found that net migration has only a minor effect on the vote share of parties strongly opposed to European integration, but a *perceived threat* from immigration has a positive effect on Euroscepticism (Lubbers and Scheepers, 2007). In one of the ultimate expressions of Euroscepticism – the UK's Brexit vote – it has been found that support for Brexit was higher in regions in decline, but that it was not decline directly that influenced the propensity to vote 'Leave' but rather that economic decline activated cultural grievances about immigration and internationalisation, which in turn drove up the Leave vote (Carreras et al., 2019; cf. Schoene, 2019). Finally, there is some evidence that regions which have received a lot of investment from EU cohesion policy tend to have lower votes for Eurosceptic parties (Rodríguez-Pose and Dijkstra, 2021) and higher support for the EU (Mahler et al., 2000; Chalmers and Dellmuth, 2015).

In all this, we are looking at the level of the sub-national region, operationalised variously as NUTS-2 or NUTS-3 regions. It is, of course, possible to identify border regions as those NUTS-2 regions that lie adjacent to a border, but at the cost that most of Germany and Sweden, to name but two examples, end up as border regions. More generally, comparative studies such as these must rely on consistent one-size-fits-all measures of Euroscepticism, such as vote share of Eurosceptic parties or responses to opinion polls. But even in the explanations for varying levels of Euroscepticism, we are looking at purely compositional explanations of regional phenomena. By focusing on abstract variables on the ground, such as the Gini coefficient, changes in unemployment rates or changes in GNI, there is not much space for narratives and how they may arise from the bottom up in local contexts. These arguments touch on a conceptual and methodological debate between political scientists such as King (1996) and Maxwell (2019) and geographers such as Agnew (1996). According to King, geographical context matters little and mostly boils down to compositional effects of individuals clustered in space. Agnew, in contrast, argues that the causes of social and political behaviour are rooted in variegated geographical contexts as much as they are in individuality: such an understanding 'would presume geographic variation in the reasons and causes of political activity.' (Agnew, 1966: 166; see also Books and Prysby, 1988). This is important for Euroscepticism: as shown above, the local effects of integration are often directly related to Eurosceptic attitudes, but of a locally grown variety that is much more nuanced than general hard or soft Euroscepticism (Durand et al., 2020, 588-589).

5.2 Euroscepticism and borders

There has been a lot of research linking Euroscepticism and borders. This comes in two strands that we might call 'Euroscepticism about the border' and 'Euroscepticism at the border'. 'Euroscepticism about the border' pertains to the instrumentalisation of borders— be they state borders ones or the external borders of the EU – by political actors for political ends.

Examples include studies of the Alternative for Germany, a party that seized on the refugee crisis to claim that the external EU borders were unsecured and that, therefore, Germany should close its own borders (Roch, 2023). In France, borders were similarly instrumentalised by the then Front National (Ivaldi, 2018). More generally and touching on the aforementioned instrumentalisation of Euroscepticism for political ends, borders are sometimes mobilised by populists to whip up nativist public sentiment (Lamour and Varga, 2020).

The second strand – ‘Euroscepticism at the border’ – concerns the question of whether people living in border regions tend to be more Eurosceptic than those located farther from the borders, or less. On this, there is some controversy: some studies show that the closer one lives to a border, the more support there is for European integration (Schmidberger, 1997; Gabel, 1998; Díez Medrano, 2003; Kuhn 2012). In contrast, other studies suggest negative effects (Decoville and Durand, 2019; Sohn and Scott, 2020; Lauener and Bernhard, 2023; Nasr and Rieger, 2023; Parker, 2013; Jacobs and Kooij, 2013; Durand et al., 2020) or differential effects depending on which side of the border is considered (Decoville and Durand, 2019; Kuhn, 2012; Durand et al., 2020, 590-1). Interestingly, those studies that are based on the Agnew-like examination of qualitative bottom-up effects (Sohn and Scott, 2020; Jacobs and Kooij, 2013; Durand et al., 2020) rather than King-like analyses of compositional effects (Gabel, 1998; Kuhn, 2012) come down on the side of border regions as areas where Euroscepticism is clearly evident.

Borders are symbolically and practically entwined with the European integration process, and some scholars have connected European integration with politicians’ and citizens’ positions on borders (Mazzoleni, 2023; Lauener, 2023; Bürkner, 2020). In border regions, idealism about the erosion of borders can exist side by side with a Euroscepticism that develops locally in border regions (Bürkner, 2020; Durand et al., 2020; Jacobs and Kooij, 2013; Parker, 2013). In some regions, highly localised negative impacts directly derived from EU-related processes of debordering and re-bordering (e.g. border closures) have been shown to strengthen popular Eurosceptic attitudes (Durand et al., 2020, 588-589).

It is important to take this localised message seriously. Following from Agnew’s approach and from the dictum that ‘although Euroscepticism is a transnational European phenomenon, opposition to the EU is sensitive to, and situated within, national cultural contexts’ (Dutceac Segesten and Bossetta, 2014, 2), one must investigate locally grown variants of Euroscepticism. People are rooted in geographical and social contexts that shape their experiences and their perceptions, and these contexts include not just the national or NUTS-2 or -3 levels but also the more local level of the border region. In addition to finding out more about the geographical distribution of Euroscepticism, it is therefore crucial to analyse the localised reasons for, and nuances of, Euroscepticism.

5.3 Euroscepticism at ‘our’ borders

There is some literature on Euroscepticism in our case study countries (e.g. Harmsen, 2010; Roch, 2023; Scott, 2020; Riishøj, 2007; Csehi and Zgut, 2021; Sunnus, 2004; Fitzgibbon, 2013) as well as studies that cover regions and, by implication or explicitly, border regions, but often this is not related specifically to the borderlands, least of all the question of how local conditions, histories etc. might shape specific Euroscepticisms.

In the **Franco-German** border region, we can draw on one important analysis by Kuhn (2012). She shows that Germans living close to France are significantly less Eurosceptic than Germans living in core Germany. However, no corresponding effect for living close to the border was found on the French side (Kuhn, 2012). Further analysis showed that it is not location per se that has the effect but rather greater transnational activities among German borderlanders (Kuhn, 2012). This differential effect ties in with the aforementioned differential effect, which suggests that different local narratives that develop from the bottom up are at play, which would also go beyond the compositional effects that Kuhn identifies.

There is no literature that we are aware of specifically on Euroscepticism in the **Øresund border region** between Sweden and Denmark. Euroscepticism in the two *countries* has been covered, though with no reference to the border (Dutceac Segesten and Bossetta, 2014). Related specifically to the border, Svensson and Nilson (2023) show that Europe is no more than an afterthought in cross-border region-building in the Øresund. This cooperation is framed as Nordic cooperation, despite attempts of the EU to tack on.

There has been a little more work on Euroscepticism in the **Polish-Czech-German** border region, with a particular focus on the German side. Here, a clash between top-down enthusiasm for the EU and sullen local responses to the concrete results of European integration on the ground in a region in decline has been noted (Dürschmidt, 2006; Bürkner, 2020). Indeed, Dürschmidt (2006, 251) describes this as ‘latent Europhobia in everyday life on the other.’

On the Polish and Czech side, Euroscepticism is more ‘Euroscepticism about the border’. As in Hungary, there was much resistance to the way the refugee crisis was handled, as opening the borders to people from the Middle East was cast as a security threat and as a threat to European civilisation (Nourbakhsh et al., 2020; Csehi and Zgut, 2020; Wondreys, 2021). More generally, the Polish-German and Czech-German borders share the historical legacy of the post-war forced population movements and - in the Polish-German case, boundary shifts - that followed the brutal German occupation period. As a result, fears of German irredentism associated with the borders and a more general suspicion of Germany should be mentioned (Galasiński and Meinhof, 2002; Cordell and Wolff, 2005). This said, in terms of ‘Euroscepticism at the border’ the Polish and Czech border regions with Germany are not strongholds of Euroscepticism, in contrast to the German border region with the two eastern neighbours.

There is a rich literature on Euroscepticism in East Central Europe, and specifically in **Hungary and Slovakia**, but little that specifically focuses on the two countries’ borderlands. However, one can make some connections between geographical factors such as the sizeable Hungarian minority in Slovakia’s border regions with Hungary, the two countries’ policies towards this minority, and EU actions and inactions within and beyond East Central Europe that touch on Euroscepticism.

On the Hungarian side, criticism of the EU is partly a political tactic, but Euroscepticism is also motivated by disappointment with the concrete effects of European integration on the ground and discontent with several mainstream EU policies, including ‘dissatisfaction with the EU’s perceived lack of active support for Hungarian minority rights’ (Scott 2020, 665; see also Tárnok, 2022), something acutely relevant to the borderlands.

On the Slovak side, the ‘Hungarian question’ associated with the Hungarian minority has sometimes been linked with Euroscepticism. In the late 1990s, Slovakia’s European integration temporarily halted not least due to its institutionalised discrimination of its ethnic minorities, including the Hungarians (Nosko, 2008, 20). Hungary’s kin-state policy (e.g. granting Hungarian citizenship or the provision of financial aid to Hungarian diaspora communities) as well as minority empowerment through funds such as the EU’s regional development funds created a backlash against minority accommodation and was mobilised by far-right parties (Hlatky, 2021; see also Bustikova, 2014). Yet while the ‘Hungarian question’ was securitised from the time of Slovakia’s independence, it became de-securitised in the early 2010s. While this was also contingent on intergovernmental relations, the most important milestone was the 2015 refugee crisis, which replaced as ‘the Hungarian’ as the ‘Other’ with ‘the migrant’ and, by implication, the EU (Kazharski, 2018, 772). Indeed, an older study on the political patterns of ethnic Hungarians in Slovakia showed that some of them, despite sympathising with far-right parties in Hungary, end up voting far-right Slovak parties (Ravasz, 2013). Ravasz (2013, 66) attributes this to ‘shared Euroscepticism overriding ideological preferences’. In short, in the Slovak-Hungarian border region, Euroscepticism is associated with the border insofar as it touches on the Hungarian minority in Slovakia’s border region with Hungary, but it can also be a unifying phenomenon akin to the reasoning ‘my enemy’s enemy is my friend’, where the EU functions as the enemy.

5.4. Outlook

To conclude, this section has shown that we must be mindful of Eurosceptic narratives being intertwined with populist strategies and right-wing and left-wing ideologies but avoid a blanket conflation of concepts. Thus, Euroscepticism must be defined broadly as general as well as issue-specific critiques of European integration, and this can vary between, as well as within, our case study regions.

Clearly, we need to examine these dynamics for our respective case study regions, where there has been a dearth of research linking local background, the border and Euroscepticism. More generally, we need to ask the following: is there a specificity to Euroscepticism in border regions? What, if any, place- and context-specific factors in turn shape perceptions of the EU? For example, a history of contestation, particular perceptions of local heritage, and the specific effects of debordering and re-bordering in a region might have a bearing on Eurosceptic attitudes.

6. Perception of Europe by minorities in selected borderlands

The interrelation between national minorities and Europe has been the focus of a great deal of research, in focusing primarily on narratives, identities, and political attitudes. This section presents an overview of the different perceptions of Europe, and the European Union in particular, that can be identified in the existing body of minority studies literature. We categorise the findings from minority studies into typologies of perceptions of Europe that are drawn from European studies. These main typologies are: Europe as a promoter of minorities, Europe as an institutional and identity resource, and Europe as an arbitrator in conflicts. This

typology helps us to present the state of the art within the minority-related literature before we set out the rationale and approach of the present B-Shapes study.

6.1. Europe as a promoter of minorities

Europe and the EU have been described as a defender and promoter of minorities and minority rights. This has been emphasised in academic works on the standard setting on minority rights by the Council of Europe (Constantin, 2017, Hofmann et al., 2018), the EU accession process of applicant states (Malloy, 2022) and the support for the Roma (Ram, 2022). Through the Copenhagen Criteria 1993, minority protection conditionality was placed on candidate states to protect their national minorities before they would be considered eligible for membership. This was particularly applied to Central and Eastern European countries who were granted accession to the EU in 2004 and 2007. While the Copenhagen criteria brought a new emphasis on minority politics, this conditionality, however, was only applied to applicant countries, and not to existing member states. There is therefore a gap between certain old members states, such as France and Greece, and new member states regarding minority protection. Furthermore, some countries were accepted as members without meeting all conditions, and this can be seen as a weak and unclear approach which has been scrutinised (Malloy, 2022). Critical scholars have also argued that the EU has only foregrounded the importance of minority rights when engaged in debates surrounding enlargement (Constantin, 2017; Nagy & Vizi, 2022). They criticise that the EU does not have adequate instruments to deal with minority issues and that the protection of autochthonous minorities has become a marginal interest (Constantin, 2017).

While not being addressed to minorities per se, EU policies of de-bordering have also had major impacts on minorities living in the borderlands of EU member states. EU de-bordering, such as Schengen, the single market or cohesion policy, are crucial for minority groups because they facilitate transnational ties. Examples include funds and tools of EU cohesion policy (Engl, 2020; Engl, 2022; Hoch, 2022) which are used by minorities to implement cross-border projects and to institutionalise cross-border cooperation. These initiatives facilitate minority transnationalism and enhance exchanges between minorities and their kinstate or kin-group in neighbouring states. Balogh and Pete (2018) have found that increasing cross-border integration can promote cross-border mobility, and lead to a strengthening of cultural and economic ties. Opilowska (2017) has further stressed that EU funded cross-border projects are still needed to reduce boundaries and promote cross-border cooperation. However, Decoville and Durand (2019) have emphasised that many individuals living in borderlands can feel left out from processes of Europeanisation and can feel resentment of their European neighbours. As such, cross border regions with a high intensity of human movement do not always result in high mutual social trust between borderland populations.

6.2. Europe as an institutional and identity resource

Europe can also be conceptualised as an institutional resource in the literature. In this perception, the EU institutional framework provides specific support and resources for minorities. The European political arena also provides chances for minorities to build alliances and networks with other ethnic minorities from different regions across Europe (Waterbury,

2021, Smith et al., 2019, Waterbury, 2017). The EU parliament has a specific platform for minority rights, in the InterGroup (Nagy & Vizi, 2022). Another recent example is the European Citizens Initiative ‘Minority Safepack’ which galvanised citizen support for minority rights protection (Waterbury, 2017). However, it has also been reported that the EU’s rejection of the Minority SafePack initiative resulted in a drop in trust in the EU by national minorities and a perception of the EU as a distant institution, and a political space that has little impact on the everyday lives of citizens (Crepaz, 2014; 2020; Waterbury, 2021).

Growing support for a common European identity could also be a threat to local national minorities, as it can undermine their hyperlocal specificities and regional characteristics. For example, the EU has aimed to promote a common European identity, and sense of cultural heritage, through cultural policy which takes superiority over protecting regional diversities (Király, 2022). Previous findings have shown that the EU is often viewed less as an emotional hub, and more as an institutional resource (Chvorostov & Waechter, 2011). Tarvet (2023) has argued that during consecutive periods of crisis, including the so-termed migration crisis and the Covid-19 pandemic, national minorities have been encouraged to move away from local identities towards national and European identities.

6.3 Europe as an arbitrator in conflicts

The EU has also been perceived as an important arbitrator in reducing and overcoming minority conflicts. Studies show that regionalist parties, of which many represent national minorities or distinct ethnic communities, have been largely pro-European (Masseti & Schakel, 2021; Elias, 2008). This indicates that they perceive European membership as beneficial to their claims and rights. Furthermore, scholars have emphasised that national minorities’ institutions, through EU provided channels and platforms, can act as foreign policy agents in sub-state diplomacy and enhance peace-building initiatives (Klatt, 2017, McCall & Itçaina, 2017). However, there has been a ‘cooling down’ in support for European integration which represents a move towards Euroscepticism since the early 2000s (Masseti & Schakel 2021, 427). Furthermore, the EU has been criticised for not having a coordinated response for conflict resolution in territorial disputes within member states (Bourne, 2004), and lacking clarity in minority–kin-state relations (Waterbury, 2008). This can lead to a securitisation of minorities and can increase boundaries between the minority population and the state where they live, which can put a strain on interethnic relations (Liebich, 2019).

6.4. Conclusion

From a review of the extant literature, it can be concluded that research on national minority perceptions of Europe and European identity tends to adopt primarily a top-down approach. On the one hand they focus on the role of European institutions, instruments and policies for minorities. On the other hand, they often look at minorities through representation, such as parties, organisations etc. There is, however, a lack of research on how minorities themselves perceive Europe and on their role in narrating Europe. Building on this gap identified in the literature, the B-SHAPES project will apply a two-fold approach: first, it will assess narratives on borders and on Europe in mainstream minority media and second, compare and contrast them with the bottom-up perspectives and lived experiences of young adults belonging to minorities in borderlands.

7. Border landscapes as heritage – state of research

The European border regions comprise a research field where changes in border discourse and narratives of the border landscape can be examined. Landscape is not a new concept to border studies, instead there is long tradition of studying border landscapes, including the physical, social, cultural elements of borders (e.g., Rumley and Minghi, 1991/2014; Arreola and Curtis, 1993). Scholars have studied collective, public perceptions of border landscapes in different contexts and from different perspectives. The role of border landscapes in national iconography has been examined by Raivo (2004) and Häyrynen (2004). Timothy and Więckowski (2022) have examined the ways in which borders are viewed as cultural heritage and the heritagisation of borders for tourism. According to them, borders can be viewed as heritage in terms of national exceptionalism, dark tourism, neighbouring relationships, local heritage narratives, infrastructural landscape, and cross-border cultural resource (Timothy and Więckowski, 2022). Other authors (Prokkola, 2010; Prokkola and Lois, 2016; and Dzikowska et al., 2023) have examined the transformation and heritagisation of European border landscapes in tourism promotion. There is also relevant research on nature conservation and transboundary landscapes (Liu et al., 2020; Tenberg et al., 2012).

The literature review of European border regions shows that border landscapes have been discussed across disciplines especially with a focus on European landscape convention (Gazzola et al., 2019; Konkoly-Gyuró et al., 2018) and that numerous public narratives of borderland landscapes exist. However, there are few studies systematically focusing on borderland people's landscape narratives or even less concerning how landscape narratives inform us about perceptions of Europe and Europeanness. This absence of landscape narratives from the perspective of people living in borderlands as well as how perceptions of Europe may be manifested in the landscape narratives of borderlands calls out for more in-depth examination.

B-SHAPES will examine the European borderlandscapes, how they are lived with and perceived by different groups of people and what agencies they bring forth. The research will broaden the existing path of borderlandscape research focusing on the spatial patterns and cultural elements of landscapes (Arreola and Curtis, 1993; Rumley and Minghi, 2014) and establish new dialogue between a place-based approach and the identity-based theorisation of borders which is argued to dominate the field of border studies (Espejo, 2020). The borderlandscapes approach draws on the place-based *where* approach to borders, directing attention not merely on identity politics but also towards places: the air, land, and waters shared by borderland people. By these means, it responds to the recent call to examine the practices and physical structures and landscapes that constitute the localised, concrete character of people's experiences of borders (Espejo, 2020, xi).

The examination of border landscape narratives in B-Shapes departs from an understanding that there is not just one narrative of a border region and its landscape, but rather parallel and overlapping political and cultural narratives, some derived from the national and regional history writings, others from today's concerns (see also Agnew, 2004). Following the B-Shapes border narrative typology – public narratives, spatial narratives, personal narratives – (also Dolińska et al., 2021), border region and landscape narratives can be analytically divided as

personal and public spatial narratives. Border region narratives can be both socially shared and more personal, based on people's experiences. The examination and analysis of these narratives provides a background for understanding public spatial narratives of the border landscapes that are often part of the consciousness of people who are living in the border region; however, some narratives can be unfamiliar and even unknown to many groups of people in the region, or they can have different connotations in the minds of people.

The B-SHAPES project will complement existing studies by paying attention to border landscapes in intersections between the cultural-natural from the point of view of borderland citizens and their narratives. It is interesting to continue to study "narrative commitments" of people living on different sides of borders and belonging to different generations, how they perceive the border region and what values, experiences, memories, and problem spaces they assign to border landscapes in present (see Wyrda, 2018). To broaden the perspective, we also work with the assumption that borderlandscapes mirror the results of dynamic human–nature interactions, encompassing both material and perceived reality. We therefore take inspiration from the post-humanist turn in the social sciences (Haraway, 1991; Ferrando, 2012; Adler-Nissen, 2014). The post-humanist perspective detaches humans from the center of knowledge and agency, in attempt to undo the nature–culture divide influencing Western modernity at large, thereby opening a path to explore what people's narratives about natural-cultural landscapes can "teach us about the world". WP5 intends to bring some of the insights of the post-human turn to the foremost human-centric field of border studies.

7.1. Swedish-Finnish border landscape

There is a considerable literature in which the Swedish-Finnish border area, its history and cross-border connections are discussed in terms of a landscape and landscape transition. The literature review shows that some narratives are more dominant and crosscutting across different contexts and sites of knowledge production. At least five 'border narratives' themes are often present in the research literature focusing on the Swedish-Finnish border landscape and its historical formation.

First, the theme of a cultural borderland is present in many studies and contexts, often referring to the history and time before the border was drawn and how the region has been a home for different peoples and cultures, a landscape where different groups and their ways of living are present (Elenius, 2008; Nordberg and Kallio-Seppänen, 2010). The second key topic of discussion concerns the year 1809 when the border was established in the Peace of Fredriksham. In this this narrative, the nature and waters play a role as a scene and landscape where and how the border was drawn as the deepest and most streaming part of a river was to constitute the border line between two countries (Elenius, 2008; Pekola, 2021; Ruotsala, 2021). The third research theme relates to the divided border region, discussing how the powerful state integration policy directed at this peripheral border region has gradually led to a differentiation between the Swedish and Finnish social and economic landscapes (Elenius, 2001).

The border has caused many landscape changes and rearrangements in land use and in the built environment of the river valley. The narrative underlines the fact that before the border was drawn the parishes and the lands belonging to local farmers were located on both sides of the river, which served as a means of communication between villages. The new border

transformed the forms of trade, transportation, land use and the built environment (Hederyd, 1992; Hederyd et al., 1991; Hederyd and Alamäki, 1993). Several studies also show how it has shaped ethnic and social identities in the region (Lunden and Zalamans, 2001) and how young people perceive the border (Jukarainen, 2000). Fourth, the research focusing on cross-border cooperation describes how the border landscape has transformed in relation to both Nordic and European institutions. The transformation of the Finnish–Swedish border institution and landscape has been examined in relation to the process of European integration and geopolitical change (Prokkola, 2010; Veemaa, 2012; Jakola, 2016; Häkli, 2016). The minority perspective is taken up in the studies discussing the powerful process of linguistic and cultural assimilation that was directed at the Finnish-speaking minority Meänkieliset in the Swedish Tornio Valley border region (Elenius, 2001; 2008) as well as in the studies of cultural activism and linguistic heritage of the minority group (Ridanpää, 2011; 2014; Prokkola and Ridanpää, 2011; Wande, 2011).

7.2. The Danish-Swedish border landscape

The Danish-Swedish border region around the Øresund strait has been studied relatively extensively since the 1990s. This is due to significant policy attention to cross-border cooperation and joint region building before and after the inauguration in 2000 of the 15-km combined bridge and tunnel uniting the Danish Sjælland Island with Scania, the most southern region of Sweden and the Scandinavian peninsula. The studies have come in the form of academic scholarly literature, often published in English, but also as fact-centred and/or analytically oriented reports produced by various institutional actors, such as Øresundsinstitutet, Øresundskomiteen, the region of Scania, the Copenhagen metropolitan etc.

The literature review indicated that there is a wealth of research pertaining to the dynamics of Øresund as a binational region (Berg, 2018; Falkheimer, 2016; Hansen and Serin, 2007; Hosper, 2006; Hultman, 2007). This research has tried to identify obstacles to cross-border integration with the aim of providing policy advice on how to remove those. Thus, even if there are negative assessments of the state of integration, they are usually written from the standpoint of possible improvement. Recent research, though, usually highlights the enormous strain caused by the political events of recent years (Sohn, 2023). Many studies often inter-related with the field of business, innovation, and infrastructure, which is the subject which has received by far the most attention (Lundquist and Winther, 2006; Skjøtt-Larsen, et al., 2003; Matthiessen, 2000). There is nearly nothing published about the history and memory politics (see, however Svensson and Nilson, 2023). It features in both Danish and Swedish histories, but never as the main ‘character’ of the written piece.

Likewise marginal, but of relevance for the borderland people’s landscape narratives and how landscape narratives inform us about perceptions of Europe and Europeanness, are scholarly reflections made on how the natural environment (physical landscape) of Scania is different from the rest of Sweden. For instance, in a 2008 book chapter, the human geographer Tomas Germundsson cites the prominent Swedish 19th century author August Strindberg, who said when returning from the continent of Scania that it was a “completely foreign landscape for a stay-at-home Swede from up-country” and the early 19th century estate owner R.H. Stjernsvärd who said of Scania that it is *attached* as to Sweden is a small patch of land, “to

show Sweden what the rest of Europe looks like” (Germundsson, 2008, 157). This focus on Scania as different is interlinked with constructions of regional heritage (Germundsson, 2013). The neighbouring county of Halland has in relation to Scania historically been described as ugly and monotonous – a fact stated by numerous travellers since the early 1800s – which enhances the notion of difference: Scania as ideal and Halland as an entity without value when it comes to the landscape. During the 19th century, historians began writing up Scania and Halland as ‘eternally natural’ to Sweden both in geographical and societal terms. The Danish past was erased and displaced (Nilson and Ottenfeldt Eliasson, 2021). Another theme of interest is how urban landscape perceptions are shaped by cities (Copenhagen, Malmö, Helsingør, Helsingborg) facing each other across the distance and closeness of water that also constitutes a border (Torcelli, 2012). Finally, a note on how new technology has added new material to the study of reproduction of landscape perceptions through narratives mediated through books and mass media. A 2008 article on tourism and mobility captures well the fascination with new patterns of tourism consumption at the time.

“Instead of clicking ‘BOOK ONLINE’, the consumer can choose to click ‘SLIDE SHOW’. The screen turns black, while an indicator shows the downloading sequence beneath the words ‘tee up’. At 100%, a melody loop starts to run, characterised by a steady groove. An orange-coloured skeleton map over Europe fills the screen, where Scania has been marked in red. The map of Europe is soon exchanged for one featuring Scania in orange and a small part Denmark to show the proximity to Copenhagen Airport. Copenhagen, Malmö, Helsingborg and Kristianstad are named with red dots on the map. The mobility of the consumer is beginning to take shape; it is easy to get here, Golf in Scania is a product that covers the whole county, as a consumer you will experience it all. Denmark fades away.” (Ek and Hultman, 2008, 235)

7.3. The Danish-German border region

The Danish-German border region is most often problematised in historiographical research as a conflict-ridden region (see for instance Auge, 2023; Bröckermann, 2021; Adriansen, 2013; Frandsen, 2008; Andersen, 2008). Yet, several versions of the region’s conflict-ridden modern history exist, and such multiplicity sometimes even articulate in conflicting interpretations. The story told from either side of the state border – in Germany and Denmark respectively - has also differed tremendously up until recently, something that should be taken into consideration when exposing the background story of the region (Auge, Frandsen and Weber, 2023). In recent years, both Danish and German historiography has tried to move away from their nationally determined history writing to reconsider the region’s importance as an integrated space, rather than just the periphery of two states – and in the Danish case, a region, which was since the 19th century assigned huge importance for the national identifications (Daubjerg, 2014; Frandsen, 2022).

What is not often done, however, is to investigate borders from the perspective of the natural heritage of the region. The research done concerning the region’s natural heritage is foremost from the research field of geography (Olwig and Olwig, 2021; Meier, 2019; Olwig, 2008) and does not explicitly focus on the aspect of bordering. A similar thing can be said when research is historiographic, relating the natural habitat to cultural history; the bordering aspect is as

good as absent. Moreover, it is mainly museums that have carried out the historiographical research around the region's natural-cultural heritage, focusing on the influence of shipping and trade on the region's West coast (Wadden Sea area) throughout history (Wollmer et. al., 2001). This historiographical tradition rarely intersects with and influences the mainstream historiographical research mentioned above and we therefore believe there is much to gain from looking into narratives produced in the relation between natural and cultural heritage in the Danish-German border region.

7.4 The Bulgarian borderlands

The Bulgarian border community, historically connected to three neighbouring countries, Bulgaria, Turkey and Greece, has been studied from different perspectives, highlighting also different identities and ethnic belongings of border communities (Dawson, 2012). Many authors focus on the repressions during the communist era and the reflection on the modern society and the new relations between the minorities and the Bulgarians (see e.g., Benovska-Sabkova and Nedin, 2016; Dragostinova, 2016), and the attempts to assimilate the Bulgarian Muslims (Pomaks) living in the border regions (Neuburger, 2000; Benovska-Sabkova, 2006). The history, traditions, cultural heritage as well as heritage politics of the region have also been examined in connection to migration (Ganeva-Raycheva, 2012). Another relevant area of research is the development of Bulgaria as a member of the European Union. For example the reforms connected with the integration processes and new cross-border connections and partnerships between Bulgaria and its neighbouring countries (Колев, 2008). As Benovska-Sabkova and Nedin (2016, 25-26) argue, Bulgarian-EU internal "borders transform themselves into bridges after opening the border checkpoint in 2010, by reviving trade, tourism, cross-border cooperation and through the resumption of everyday communication between people on both sides of the border fence."

8. Conclusions

The aim of the report was to provide an overview of the state of the art on borderlanders' perceptions of Europe and the European project, to identify the main research gaps and to provide the basis for the empirical part of the B-SHAPES project. A particular focus of the report was directed at the themes that organise our research in the WPs: Euroscepticism in the borderlands, minorities' perceptions of Europe, and borderlands as natural and cultural landscapes. The report paid particular attention also to the most important contemporary events that acted as possible game changers in the public perception of Europe: bordering during the 'migration crisis' and COVID-19 pandemic and the political debate in the European Parliament (with special emphasis on the campaign during the European election in 2019). In the Conclusion, we summarise the main findings from the state of the art:

Borderlands perception of Europe in the context of the migration crisis

- The securitisation of borders and transformations of border regimes shifted the understanding of the European borderlands from a geographical/localised meaning to more de-territorialised and dynamic ones. While the literature examined the perceptions and voices of many

inhabitants and agents of such borderlands (e.g. migrants, activists, regional elites active in cross-border cooperation), and brought attention to how everyday life and activism of borderlands sometimes challenged re-bordering, what is lacking is the public perception of Europe in traditional borderlands in the context of border transformations.

- The state of the art does not give the possibility of comparing the perceptions of Europe in various borderlands, and it fails to offer analysis of changes in these perceptions in the context of the 'migration crisis'.
- The link between specific techniques and narratives of bordering and the shifting perceptions of Europe is also missing in the current literature.

Borderlanders' perceptions of Europe in the context of the Covid-19 pandemic

- The literature on bordering during the COVID-19 pandemic describes various mobilisations and reactions of the public to border closures and new sanitary measures. However, more long-lasting effects of these processes on the stance of the borderlanders towards re/debordering, and their impact on the perceptions of Europe, remain to be examined.
- The possible influence of Covid-19 on the political narratives on Europe and borders during the coming European Elections 2024 needs to be analysed as well.
- It is important to examine whether the Covid-19 crisis will act as a booster of cross-border cooperation and the possibilities forenhanced European identification, which appears to be wishful-thinking on the part of stakeholders involved in cross-border cooperation.

European elections – political groups in the European Parliament and their perception of re/debordering

- An analysis of European Union policies and the different approaches of the political groups in the European Parliament shows that border issues remain at the centre of interest not only for voters but also for their representatives at the level of EU bodies. Contemporary political challenges such as migration crisis and armed conflicts at Europe's borders, as well as humanitarian crises and poverty, have influenced the dynamics of the discussion on the internal and external borders of the European Union. This topic has become one of the challenges facing the European Parliament in recent years.
- At the same time, despite their declared different approaches to border issues, the parties present in the European Parliament were quite united in making decisions on some of these challenges, showing a far-reaching willingness to compromise. Although the statements pointed out the omissions of the opposing political groups, in the end, various laws were passed and there are many signals that this topic will not disappear from the voters' and politicians' attention in the next elections either.

Euroscepticism at the Borderlands

- The literature on Euroscepticism stresses the role that borders play in Eurosceptic narratives and mobilisations, especially those of a populist nature. At the same time, the state of the art offers divergent views on the character of Euroscepticism in the borderlands. Especially the most general issue – are borderlands more Eurosceptic than other regions or are they more resilient to Eurosceptic narratives? – remains a puzzle. Even more importantly, what are local flavours of Euroscepticism, and how – if at all – do these ties in with narratives about the border? The comparative analysis – provided by the B-SHAPES project – should let us address this research gap.

- Moreover, the possible link between recent phases of de/re-bordering and borderlands' Euroscepticism remains unexamined, too.

Perception of Europe by minorities in selected borderlands

- The main limitation of the state of the art on this issue is a top-down approach. Minorities' perceptions of Europe are mainly studied as the products of European institutions and policies. A bottom-up perspective is much needed to supplement the picture.
- The second limitation is the reduction of the voices of borderland minorities vis-a-vis official and institutionalised representatives. Such an approach downplays the eventuality in which the minorities are not necessarily adequately represented by their political or media channels.
- The literature does not offer general findings about the minoritarian view of Europe, and it lacks also the comparative resources to examine the similarities and differences between European borderlands.

Borders landscapes as heritages

- The research on borderlandscapes to date was focused mainly on the identities of borderlanders who inhabit them. The attention given to the concrete places and natural-cultural intersections in the landscape played a more marginal role.
- Moreover, the emphasis was given to the most expressive narratives in the borderlands, downplaying how various narratives overlap, and how the different types of narratives – public, spatial, or personal – coexist in one landscape.
- Another limitation in the literature is the lack of research on European narratives in borderland landscapes.

In conclusion, this report has highlighted significant research gaps in understanding borderlanders' perception of Europe and the European project. As the B-SHAPES project aims to address these gaps, it will provide valuable insights into Euroscepticism, minorities' perspectives, and the heritage of border landscapes in shaping the future of Europe.

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